

A Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework: The Development, Implementation and Evaluation

MSc in Computer Science

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ABSTRACT

Since the inception of cloud computing, it has gained a tremendous pace. Several companies seeking more profit are searching for various means to move their applications to the cloud from their on-premise infrastructure. Academics and professionals have devised a variety of Cloud migration strategies in order to assist companies with their migration efforts. Nevertheless, the applicability of these strategies varies based on Cloud Service Provider to which the workload/application is migrated. Organisations are therefore forced to adhere to specific migration rules tailored to services offered by public cloud service providers. Due to this reason, organisations evaluating various service providers may find it challenging because of the complexities emanating from evaluating several cloud migration strategies. This migration strategy evaluation process complicates the decision-making process for companies or organisations. This dissertation aims to develop an unbiased, comprehensive approach/framework to cloud migration initiatives. A Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF) is developed within this dissertation for seamless cloud migration. Design Science Research (DSR) was the qualitative research approach utilised. This research approach was used because the actual outcome of the research is a problem-solving innovation. The CCMF was developed, implemented and evaluated using the DSR approach with an adaptive test case. Based on the artefact evaluation, the CCMF is an effective solution for cloud migration challenges. CCMF can assist organisations in making the right decisions regarding cloud migration and is also a significant addition to the research community.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ASP	Application Service Provider
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BSC	Balanced ScoreCard
CCMF	Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DSR	Design Science Research
FED	Framework for Evaluation in Design Science
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Organisation of Standardisation
IT	Information Technology
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
PaaS	Platform as a Service
RFD	Requirement for Framework Design
SaaS	Software as a Service
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
UK	United Kingdom
VM	Virtual Machine
XaaS	Anything as a Service

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Cloud computing is the delivery of cloud services, using data centres and server farms to provide on-demand tools and services through the internet (Sultan, 2010). Cloud computing permits access to data and applications regardless of the underlying hosting infrastructure. Service providers like Google, Amazon, and Microsoft monitor and manage these data centres. The emergence of cloud computing was a result of the combination of various technologies. Cloud computing illustrates the progress of existing technology and computing methodologies (Lampe et al., 2012). Cloud service providers, individuals, and organisations have the potential to take advantage of cloud computing (Vinoth et al., 2022). When discussing "organisations" in this dissertation, this refers to organisations that are considering moving applications to the cloud from on-premises infrastructure. Also, on-premises workload/application refers to applications housed in the organisation's data centre.

1.2 Research Background

Cloud computing offers companies inexpensive, extensible, and dynamic technologies (Nedbal et al., 2014). Cloud computing customers do not own the underlying hardware. Instead, they pay a third-party vendor to use it. They use resources on a subscription basis and only pay for what they use (Adebisi, Adekanmi and Oluwatobi, 2014). A pay-as-you-go model allows companies to precisely meet their demands for computing capabilities as activities vary, rather than scaling on-premises infrastructure for extreme situations (Tak, Uргаonkar and Sivasubramaniam, 2011). In this manner, Cloud Computing lowers IT infrastructure costs by eliminating the need for hardware procurement and servicing as well as software upgrades and licensing (Yeboah-Boateng and Essandoh, 2014). Cloud computing can be deployed in four ways: private, public, community, and hybrid. The public cloud is perhaps the most popular deployment approach comprising cloud service providers like Amazon, IBM and Google, giving cheap or free cloud services, according to Chou (2015). It is important to note that there are three types of cloud-based services: software as a service, platform as a service and infrastructure as a service (Schneider and Sunyaev, 2016).

In order to take full advantage of cloud computing, organisations must develop plans for migrating their on-premises workloads to the cloud. An organisation must choose the applications that best fit into the Cloud infrastructure before moving current applications over (Panori et al., 2016). The cloud service providers offer application migration methods

through policies, processes, and guidelines that apply to particular application types and Cloud infrastructures. For instance, Amazon offers guidelines for moving particular applications to the AWS Cloud in a set of publications referred to as the AWS Prescriptive Guidance (AWS Prescriptive Guidance, 2022). For Microsoft, we have the Microsoft Cloud Adoption Framework for Azure (Microsoft, 2022). RedHat (RedHat, 2022) and IBM (IBM, 2022) also take the same path by offering guidance on transferring particular workloads to their respective Cloud hostings. However, cloud service provider's frameworks do not provide a comprehensive cloud adoption strategy across multiple platforms. This creates limitations in having a seamless and clear understanding of Cloud migration.

Several researchers have also put forth various Cloud adoption strategies, just like Cloud Services Providers. According to Varia (2010), an application/workload list could be used as a preliminary step for cloud adoption. An organisation can identify the workloads viable for Cloud migration by reviewing such workloads as some are not suitable for migration. For instance, Older and third-party applications are more difficult to move to the cloud compared to Email, Office 365 and collaborative tools, which are everyday business applications. Furthermore, because multi-purpose applications do not have any features that are exclusive to a company, they are excellent choices for cloud adoption (Martson et al., 2011). The Beserra et al. (2012) migration strategy views organisational limitations associated with the objectives, regulations, standards, processes, and laws as the initial phase that could affect the capability to embrace Cloud technologies. The numerous Cloud migration approaches present a difficulty for academicians and professionals because it is challenging for them to assimilate, understand, and integrate (Ellison, Calinescu and Paige, 2018).

1.3 Research Question

The research questions associated with this dissertation were coined from a statement of the problem focused on the absence of a standardised method for moving on-premises workloads/applications to the cloud. It is evident from the various Cloud migration strategy that there is no universal framework for moving applications to the cloud from on-premises infrastructure. Organisations intending to move their workload to the cloud must adhere to specific migration rules established by various Cloud service providers. These rules have resulted in debates over the ideal migration procedure to use. As a result, a Cloud migration procedure that does not rely on a specific approach developed by a Cloud Service Provider is required. In order to establish a comprehensive framework, the following research questions come to bear.

- What are the difficulties associated with migrating workloads or applications to the cloud from on-premise?
- What criteria must be fulfilled before deciding to transition to the cloud?
- What are the targeted motives and reasons for migration within an organisation?
- What criteria determine which migration strategy best suits a particular application?

1.4 Motivation

Several companies seeking more profit are searching for various means to move their applications to the cloud from their on-premise infrastructure seamlessly. The motivation behind developing a universal framework for cloud migration comes from a clear understanding of the benefits of cloud computing and cloud migration challenges. This framework is developed to achieve seamless cloud migrations into any cloud platform.

1.5 Aim

The aim of this research is to develop, implement and evaluate a comprehensive cloud migration framework.

1.6 Objectives

The objectives of this dissertation are stated below;

- Literature review on cloud computing, cloud migration frameworks and their limitations
- To analyse the motives and reasons for migration within an organisation.
- Develop a Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF).
- Implement an on-premise migration to the cloud using the Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF).

1.7 Deliverables

The deliverables from this dissertation are outlined below,

- A literature review on cloud computing, cloud migration frameworks and their limitations.
- A Comprehensive cloud migration framework.
- Implement a cloud migration using the comprehensive cloud migration framework (CCMF).
- The findings of the CCMF efficacy evaluation.
- Dissertation Report.

1.8 Structure of Dissertation

The dissertation is structured into chapters, as shown in Figure 1. Chapter 1 covers the research background, questions, aims, objectives and deliverables of having a comprehensive cloud migration framework (CCMF). Chapter 2 offers an overview of what Cloud Computing is, its features, the drivers, requirements, advantages, difficulties, migrating approaches, and challenges. The research problem and method are discussed in Chapter 3. The main objective of this chapter is to provide a quick overview of the research problem and a rationale for the selected research strategy. Chapter 4 analyses the problem associated with cloud migration issues and will be looked into more critically. Chapter 5 presents the artefact design. Details about the artefact's background are presented as a series of interconnected building blocks put together to develop the artefact. Chapter 6 delivers an implementation of cloud migration using the comprehensive cloud migration framework (artefact). Furthermore, chapter 7 critically evaluates the artefact's efficacy by getting feedback via interviews with experienced cloud computing stakeholders and professionals. Finally, the conclusion explains how the objectives were actualised and provide recommendations for future research.

Figure 1: Dissertation Structure

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The literature review is approached by systematically searching related articles from Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore and Staffordshire University Libraries database. Google Scholar offers research articles for scholars and researchers. At the same time, the Staffordshire University Libraries repository (Staffordshire University Libraries, 2022), IEEE Xplore and other academic open libraries feature more academic research papers. Including content from researchers, professionals and academics was critical, as they all offer advice on Cloud services and migration.

2.2 Cloud Computing Overview

Cloud computing is a concept that gives Internet-accessible services. These services can exchange, administer, and save data housed on servers remotely rather than on servers on-premises or on personal computers (Foster et al., 2009). According to Beserra et al. (2012), cloud computing provides a way of using virtual computer capabilities as a pay-as-you-go delivery which can be accessed over the internet remotely. These virtualised computing capabilities consist of readily available technology, software and applications development Infrastructure (Zhao and Zhou, 2014). In contrast to the conventional on-premise IT structure, in which organisations have and manage every infrastructure, the cloud allows for the provision of IT resources over the Internet (Feuerlicht, Burkon and Sebesta, 2011). The cloud is the network of data centres that houses these computer resources (Armbrust et al., 2009).

Furthermore, even though there is no universal Cloud computing definition, the most commonly referenced definition is given by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, 2016) (Mell and Grace, 2011). NIST defines cloud computing as a concept for enabling easy, functional and available access to a shared pool of reconfigurable computational resources. These resources include servers, networks, applications, and storage, which may be deployed rapidly and delivered with minimal administration effort or service provider intervention. Figure 2 shows three distinct service models, four deployment types, and five fundamental attributes that makeup cloud computing (NIST, 2016) (Mell and Grace, 2011). These features will be discussed in subsequent sub-chapters.

Figure 2: Cloud computing model, deployment type and attributes (NIST, 2016)

2.3 The Service Models of Cloud Computing

In the past, IT services were provided through on-site infrastructure. Presently, they are offered as Anything as a Service (XaaS) by using the internet to access such services (Miyachi, 2018). According to Robison (2008), Anything as a Service relates to services which will or have been moved to the cloud. While (Taleb, Ksentini and Jantti, (2016) regarded this as the totality of all cloud deployable services. However, Everything as a Service is how Rahko (2016) refers to Anything as a service (XaaS). As shown in Figure 3, the common services delivered through the cloud are classified into three: Infrastructure as a service – IaaS, Platform as a service – PaaS and Software as a service – SaaS (RedHat, 2022).

Infrastructure as a service (IaaS) is a cloud computing service offered as a platform in a virtualised environment. The purchase of computers, network infrastructure, or workspace is not required of customers (Alouffi et al., 2021). The Cloud service provider is in charge of purchasing, maintaining and upgrading the infrastructure. Even though an organisation does not control or manage services like the firewall, which is part of the network infrastructure, it can manage resources such as storage, operating system and applications which have been deployed (Mell and Grace, 2011). A notable advantage of IaaS is that the CSP utilises cutting-edge

technology, enabling organisations to improve service delivery and product development time (Rimal et al., 2011). Several Cloud service providers deliver IaaS capabilities, like Amazon EC2 service from AWS (2022) and Azure Virtual machines from Microsoft (2022).

Figure 3: Shows the Management structure of each Service Model (Chen, 2020)

- Platform as a service (PaaS) offers a cloud computing solution that integrates well with the software development lifecycle. This service facilitates the creation of cloud-based services and applications (Dillon, Wu and Chang, 2010). The PaaS Cloud service's ready-to-use tools allow organisations to generate new goods and services more quickly and concentrate on developing functional applications while the CSP takes care of the Cloud (Kavis, 2014). Furthermore, rather than application developers bothering with purchasing equipment, the CSP equipment is used for application delivery via the internet. In PaaS, organisations do not need to acquire hardware and software components to build applications. PaaS paradigm examples include AWS Elastic Beanstalk, Google App Engine, Heroku, and Windows Azure (Alouffi et al., 2021).
- Software as a service (SaaS) makes it easier for customers to employ cloud-based software and other applications. The SaaS solution removes the requirement for setting up on-premises storage systems, applications, and infrastructure maintenance. The cloud service provider is in charge of all but a few application configuration parameters related to a single or group of users. Organisations only pay for SaaS resources used (Jamsa, 2012). Customers can access SaaS applications via various technologies, including application interfaces and browsers (Mell and Grace, 2011). SaaS is also an Application

Service Provider (ASP) and a new delivery mechanism for software (Rimal et al., 2011). Applications like Google Workspace, GoToMeeting, Dropbox, Gmail, Cisco WebEx, Salesforce, and various other applications accessible via the internet are among the most popular SaaS (Li et al., 2014). The CSP is responsible for ensuring outstanding services and protecting customers' information, unlike on-premise infrastructure, where the organisation is responsible (Hugos and Hulitzky, 2010).

2.4 The Deployment Models of Cloud Computing

A deployment model defines the purpose and use of the cloud. Cloud computing definition reflects on the deployment models in use (Hashemi and Bardsiri, 2012). According to NIST, we have four cloud deployment models: Community, Private, Public and Hybrid (Mell and Grance, 2011). When an organisation decides to move to the cloud, it can select the optimal deployment model for its business needs (Kumalo and van der Poll, 2018).

In a Public Cloud, multiple consumers can utilise a cloud service provided by a particular cloud service provider. The CSP's facilities are the location of the Public Cloud, which is developed specifically for public usage (Mell and Grace, 2011). The CSP owns and operates the public cloud and is capable of offering some types of services for free. An example of such services is the popular Gmail from Google (Vignos, Kim and Metzger, 2013). An organisation using the public cloud does not possess total control over its data. However, it could reduce the risk associated with such by keeping data that are critical in its private infrastructure and the less critical data in the public cloud (Strauch et al., 2012). Furthermore, the public cloud also provides a pay-per-use structure, requiring the user to only make payments for what has been used (Jadeja and Modi, 2012).

A Private Cloud can be located on or off the organisation's buildings and is intended for one organisation's exclusive usage, with various users utilising the Cloud (Mell and Grace, 2011). One of the main benefits of a private cloud is its ease of handling maintenance, security, software updates, usage and deployment (Jadeja and Modi, 2012). Privacy is kept because the organisation controls its data (Shoniwa, 2016). Another advantage of the private cloud over the public cloud is that there are little or no concerns about the privacy and security of data (Kavis, 2014). However, the private cloud offers lesser advantages with respect to scalability and cost savings, though easier to comply with regulatory obligations (Carroll, Van Der Merwe and Kotze, 2011).

Community cloud gives access to a particular array of organisations which are part of the same community and have common objectives. This is because such organisations' privacy settings, applications, security policies and performance are all the same (Baiardi and Sgandurra, 2010). Furthermore, Vignos et al. (2013) also clarify that several organisations with the same goal share a community cloud, which helps keep costs down. One of several benefits of community cloud is that it improves collaboration amongst enterprises and increases productivity (Fernández et al., 2012). There are certain drawbacks to a community cloud, such as bandwidth and storage sharing, and it can also be more expensive than a public cloud (Goyal, 2014).

The advantages of public, private, and community clouds are combined in a hybrid cloud. This kind of cloud computing lets organisations combine the other deployment models in a way that works for them (Weinman, 2016). A hybrid cloud has great scalability, flexibility, and security. In order to achieve the best results, a hybrid cloud should utilise the public cloud whenever practical and the private cloud when data security and ownership are crucial (Kavis, 2014).

2.5 Technologies that Enable Cloud Computing

Cloud computing has emerged as a convergence of numerous computing models, with several technologies linked. Cloud computing improves the functioning of other technological areas with the primary purpose of obtaining effective resource use, availability, and scalability, which other technological fields only partially address (Abah and Ogwueleka, 2013). Cloud computing uses various technologies, including virtualisation, service-oriented architecture (SOA), Grid computing and utility computing (Priya, 2019).

- **Virtualisation:** This is a technology which involves the creation of a virtual-based representation of servers, applications, networks and storage in order to minimise IT costs while making sure agility and efficiency are increased (VMware, 2022). According to Sharma (2015), virtualisation makes it possible for an application to be abstracted from its physical infrastructure. Virtualisation enables sharing physical infrastructure so that companies can alter and utilise the virtualised infrastructure in the same manner as they would the physical infrastructure (Dhaya, Kanthavel and Venusamy, 2021). Furthermore, as shown in Figure 4, virtualisation is enabled by installing a thin virtualisation software known as a hypervisor on a physical machine. The hypervisor allows numerous Virtual Machines (VM) to run on a single physical machine (Cerveira, Barbosa and Madeira, 2021). Through virtualisation, organisations

can leverage cloud computing by being able to run numerous applications simultaneously. It also allows the aggregation of hardware infrastructure to serve as a resource pool and overlays (Foster et al., 2009). We have various types of virtualisation, namely Hardware, Desktop, Network Application, operating system, server, and storage virtualisation. Today, the most generally used virtualisation software is Citrix and VMware, both of which deliver a seamless experience on virtual computers (Priya, 2019).

Figure 4: Graphical representation of virtualisation concept (Mohammed and Kiran, 2014)

- **Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA):** This application separates services into discrete business operations and routine procedures. This cloud application component is exceptional because it allows cloud-related procedures to be changed and amended on demand as business demands require (Priya, 2019). In contrast to cloud computing, which provides technology solutions to enterprises, individual customers and execution of codes, SOA provides a web-based service across several applications. Furthermore, one of the benefits of SOA is its lower programming application cost because it has the functionality of reusing web services (Rittinghouse and Ransome, 2017). An SOA consists of two main parts: software as a service and quality as a service. Software as a service delivers a new software delivery paradigm that is derived from the service

providers' application domain, while quality as a service is to look at a service from a different perspective and determine its purpose and performance (Priya, 2019). SOA is not replaced by cloud computing but adds to the services cloud computing offers. SOA and cloud computing share the same concept of computer resources being shared. A Cloud Infrastructure that requires additional resources can obtain them without allocating physical resources. These resources, like SOA, are available on a demand basis (Mushi, 2020).

- Grid computing refers to the use of distributed systems to achieve a common aim (Priya, 2019). Grid Computing is a term used to describe the use of numerous computer processors to do tasks that demand a high amount of processing power. Grid Computing's technique for sharing resources uses middleware software that spreads an application over multiple computers (Hashemi and Bardsiri, 2012). Cloud Computing's predecessors are Grid computing and Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA). Beyond the capabilities that cloud computing already provides, these new technologies are now incorporated into cloud computing. In order to set up a cloud computing Infrastructure and technology, SOA and Grid computing are essential building blocks (Mushi, 2020).
- Utility computing: This computing paradigm specifies a pay-per-use service provisioning mechanism for services such as compute, infrastructure and storage (Priyambiga and Patil, 2021). Primarily, utility computing aids in cost reduction by lowering organisational startup costs. As an organisation's computing demands change, so does the billing change; for example, if its usage lowers, its billing cost will also fall (Priya, 2019).

2.6 Advantages of cloud computing for organisations

When an organisation moves its on-premise workloads to the cloud, it gains several benefits. The section discusses the advantages that cloud computing can give to organisations. However, this is not a comprehensive list of the advantages of cloud computing because additional Cloud services are constantly being launched.

Cost Savings: Organisations using cloud computing are only charged for the services they utilise. Also, maintenance costs are reduced because the user does not have to acquire any infrastructure. Furthermore, organisations can save money by moving their data centres to the cloud, which lowers their initial investment costs. Such savings can be reinvested in the company's core operation to improve customer service (Saini, Upadhyaya and Khandelwal, 2019). One of the significant reasons why organisations migrate to the cloud is the financial

advantage (Alharbi, Atkins and Stanier, 2017). It is unrealistic to think that Cloud services will always save money (Weinman, 2016). To further buttress this point, Weinman (2016) asked if CSPs can also save costs by using services from other CSPs. An instance is given if Amazon web services could use Google's cloud services or vice versa to save cost.

Increased Security: In the cloud, security is taken care of by the service provider, who ensures that all associated security infrastructure is regularly updated, security patches are applied, and the security level is evaluated frequently (Priya, 2019). Cloud computing provides a very high level of security by leveraging data encryption, strong security restrictions, key management, and security awareness (Aydin, 2015).

Mobility: is the ability to operate in environments where individuals connect using digital applications and infrastructures, allowing tasks to be performed anytime and anywhere (Oke et al., 2021). Through mobile devices, customers of cloud computing can access services at any time and from any location. If clients travel, they can still use the services using their laptops and mobile devices (Abdulkader and Abualkishik, 2013).

Scalability: Cloud computing resources may be scaled up and down as needed, allowing infinite processing power to be accessible (Xue and Xin, 2016). The ability to scale up resources on demand is a significant benefit of cloud computing, particularly for smaller companies (Armbrust et al., 2010). In addition, the processing capacity of cloud computing enables users to quickly and easily analyse large amounts of data. Consequently, that grabbed business analysts' attention, who are eager to study the market and forecast what customers will do next (Yumpu.com, 2011).

Availability: This refers to the operational likelihood of cloud infrastructure and the quality of its service being provided to its consumers at any given moment (Mushi, 2020). Most businesses have concerns about cloud applications' availability when they need them (Priyambiga and Patil, 2021). This increased reliance on Cloud computing necessitates a high level of service availability (Hu et al., 2014). CSPs infrastructures have been developed to deliver better availability than conventional IT infrastructure. In addition, CPSs can quickly identify and fix technical glitches, making system troubleshooting and recovery much easier (Young, 2015). Despite CSP's efforts to maintain a greater availability level, disruptions sometimes occur in CSP data centres. In February 2017, Amazon's S3 service went down, which caused AWS services in Northern Virginia to stop working (AWS, 2017).

Business Agility: In light of the increased volatility in the market and the increasing strain on organisations to manage IT-driven business development activities. Business agility is a vital organisational skill to adapt to global demands and fresh business prospects (Mikalef and Pateli, 2017). Business agility is a company's ability to adjust quickly, well, and long-term to environmental changes (Mungwini, 2018). Businesses can be more flexible because the cloud makes it easy to deploy applications quickly, which implies that businesses can instantly provide additional services. How agile an organisation is will rely on associated organisations like the CSPs. The benefits of organisational agility outweigh the costs of migrating to the Cloud (Liu et al., 2018). Organisations planning to move workloads/applications to the cloud increasingly realise that revenue growth is more important than cost reduction when making such a decision, making cloud services beneficial.

2.7 Organisational challenges of cloud computing

Cloud computing is a rapidly evolving digital technology sector gaining traction worldwide. However, despite proving its worth in the business world, educating consumers and company leaders about its challenges is necessary. Furthermore, Abeywickrama and Rosca (2015) state that organisational issues are related to the impact of compliance, regulatory and legal requirements. These requirements come into play regarding data security in tightly controlled organisations. Bassett (2015) states that significant problems associated with cloud computing are security, network latency, data privacy, statutory and legal compliance, availability, lack of standardisation and interoperability. Table 1 shows a review of cloud computing challenges from research papers. To address cloud migration framework decisions, let us discuss some major challenges: Continuity and Availability, Standards, Vendor lock-in, Reliability, and Migration Issues.

Continuity and Availability: An organisation utilising cloud computing already will depend on the CSP to access daily IT services, maintenance and support. According to Opara-Martins et al. (2014), such organisations care a lot about the continuity and availability of services, which is why cloud computing is adopted. CSPs can encounter outages like AWS (2017), which could deprive organisations of access to essential business systems. In addition, Bassett (2015) mentions the prospect of CSPs being susceptible to a malicious code attack, such as a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS), rendering cloud-based data inaccessible, compromised, or lost. Therefore, organisations are responsible for developing contingency plans to ensure their businesses' smooth running. The goal and emphasis of the ISO 22301 standard is the

continuity of an organisation's business operations following a disruptive event (Orange Business Services, 2019).

Table 1: Review of cloud computing challenges from research papers.

Sources	Security	Vendor lock-in and privacy	Management and control	Law and regulation	Portability and Interoperability	Disaster recovery	Lack of Standard and audit	Availability and Continuity
Bassett (2015)	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Nazir and Jamshed (2013)	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
Armbrust et al. (2010)	✓	✓					✓	✓
Priya (2019)	✓	✓	✓				✓	
Priyambiga and Patil (2021)	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Xue and Xin (2016)	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	
Yeboah-Boateng and Essandoh, (2014)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓

Standards in Cloud Computing: The effort to standardise the cloud is never-ending. Several technical and professional bodies have developed standards, guidelines, and recommendations for optimal Cloud Computing implementation. Some of the organisations are; Cloud Standards Customer Council (CSCC, 2022), Distributed Management Task Force (DMTF, 2022), European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI, 2022), Organisation for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS, 2022), National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, 2022), and International Organisation for Standardization (ISO, 2022). NIST and ISO are organisations that have produced a lot of standards for the cloud. Table 2 summarises some of the most often utilised cloud standards provided by two of the aforementioned standards bodies.

Table 2: A summary of some cloud computing standards.

Organisations	Standards	Areas of concentration	References
National Institutes of Standard and Technology (NIST)	NIST SP 500-293 (2011)	Cloud computing technology roadmap.	NIST SP 500-293 (2011)
	NIST SP 800-144 (2011)	Guidelines on security and privacy in public cloud computing	NIST SP 800-144 (2011)
	NIST SP 800-145 (2011)	The NIST definition of cloud computing.	NIST SP 800-145 (2011)
	NIST SP 500-291 (2011)	NIST cloud computing standards roadmap.	NIST SP 500-291 (2011)
International Organisation for Standard (ISO)	ISO/IEC 17789:2014, Information technology	Cloud computing Reference architecture.	ISO/IEC 17789:2014
	ISO/IEC 17826:2016, Information technology.	Cloud data management interface	ISO/IEC 17826:2016
	ISO/IEC 18384:2016, Information technology	Reference architecture for service oriented architecture (SOA)	ISO/IEC 18384:2016
	ISO/IEC 19941:2017, Information technology	Cloud computing interoperability and portability.	ISO/IEC 19941:2017
	ISO/IEC Technical Specification 23167:2020, Information technology	Cloud computing Common technologies and techniques.	ISO/IEC Technical Specification 23167:2020
	ISO/IEC 27017:2015, Information technology	Security techniques	ISO/IEC 27017:2015

Vendor Lock-In: This refers to a situation when clients or an organisation are tied to a particular cloud provider's technological infrastructure and cannot readily switch vendors without significant expenses, regulatory restraints, or compatibility issues (Sitaram and Manjunath, 2011). Developers observe vendor lock-in when users are exposed to any changes

their vendors make because applications designed for one cloud platform cannot be readily moved to another (Satzger et al., 2013). Quint and Kratzke (2016) suggested that Lock-in by vendors can be avoided by creating a common Cloud service description language that specifies secure, transferrable and flexible services launched on every IaaS.

Reliance on Service providers: Organisations lose a reasonably level of control over their IT infrastructure when they are handled and provided by a cloud service provider (Alosaimi and Alnuem, 2016). Organisation then relies on the Cloud Service Provider to provide daily access, support and maintenance for needed services. Monitoring performance is a major concern for organisations because they have no means of monitoring feedback from other organisations or customers, thereby leaving them to accept the performance information given by cloud service providers (Hugos and Hulitzky, 2010). Furthermore, most cloud service providers will not take responsibility for clients' data. The Microsoft Services Agreement states, " We strongly advise you to make regular backup copies of your Content. Microsoft cannot be held responsible for your Content or the material others upload, store or share using our Services " (Microsoft, 2021). However, it is essential to note that there are single points of failure outside of any hardware. A software update that affects one region could have unintended consequences across the entire system.

Challenges of Cloud Migration: To further reduce the danger of Cloud computing uncertainty, organisations are hesitant to deploy their essential applications to the cloud. This hesitation results from ambiguity in accreditation, legal certainty, standardisation, data security, vendor lock-in, and interoperability in the cloud for customer organisations (Jones et al., 2019). Furthermore, other problems and hazards have been identified by researchers when it comes to moving workloads into the cloud. This proves that additional research is needed to encourage organisations to feel confident about migrating. According to Alkhalil et al. (2016), the main obstacle to organisations moving to the cloud is insufficient information about the cloud among users.

2.8 Strategies for Cloud Migration

An organisation's high-level plans for migrating its current on-premises or co-located workloads and the data they generate into the cloud is known as a cloud migration strategy (VMware, 2022). This plan always involves a public cloud service provider's migration strategy. Amazon Web services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, and Google cloud Platform (GCP) are the most popular. Furthermore, this cloud Service providers like Amazon offers guidelines for moving particular workload/applications to the AWS Cloud in a set of publications referred to as the AWS -

Table 3: An evaluation of some frameworks for cloud migration decision-making

Framework	Critical Analysis	Reference
SMICloud: A Framework for Comparing and Ranking Cloud Services	Service Measurement Index was used to build the Service Measurement Index Cloud framework (SMICloud). With this framework, Cloud users can explore multiple Cloud services in relation to their individual needs. Since this framework is concerned with evaluating Quality of Service (QoS), it solely gave thought to the technological idea. This framework nevertheless disregards qualitative indications like organisational challenges.	(Garg, Versteeg and Buyya, 2011)
Cloud Service Selection Using Multicriteria Decision Analysis	This framework's primary objective is to evaluate the organisation's decision-making for providers of cloud-based services and cloud services. Despite the fact that the study covers the majority of MCDA techniques while also being extensively reported, it only concentrates on the technological and deployment components. Some significant issues, like guidelines and higher-level strategic perspectives, were not indicated.	(Whaiduzzaman et al., 2014)
Assessing Cloud Readiness with Magic Matrices Method	The Magic Matrices Method is a tool for figuring out how ready organisations are for the cloud. Through an investigation of certain Technological services, the Magic Matrices Approach relies on an organisation's level of operation. Despite the fact that this approach offers a good grasp of the technology perspective of adopting cloud computing, It concentrates largely on the operations and not the strategy aspect of making decisions.	(Loebbecke, Thomas and Ullrich, 2011)
Cloud Computing Strategic Planning (HC ² SP) model	This framework has been developed to serve as a roadmap for medical institutions interested in implementing cloud computing technologies. For health organisations thinking of migrating from a conventional medical approach to cloud-based solutions, this framework could function similarly to a SWOT analysis. The framework does not address the process of making decisions.	(Kuo, 2011)
OPTIMIS: A holistic approach to cloud service provisioning	The framework was developed using a comprehensive method for providing Cloud computing services. Though researchers were particularly interested in the perspectives of two interested parties: providers of infrastructure and service. While this research's comprehensive methodology will benefit providers of service, it won't do anything to benefit users of Cloud Services.	(Ferrer et al., 2012)

Prescriptive Guidance (AWS Prescriptive Guidance, 2022). For Microsoft, we have the Microsoft Cloud Adoption Framework for Azure (Microsoft, 2022) and Google Cloud Adoption Framework (Google Cloud, 2022). RedHat (RedHat, 2022), IBM (IBM, 2022). Although cloud migrations are advantageous for the majority of workloads, some others are not ideal for the cloud (Cisco, 2022). Gartner (2011) clarifies that an organisation's intention to migrate must be explicit and align with underlying IT and business objectives. The choice to move to the cloud is driven by business considerations, which involve risks, giving it a broader scope than technical considerations (Alkhalil et al., 2016). As Jamshidi et al. (2015) point out, cloud migration has no one-size-fits-all approach. To further give a clear perspective to this dissertation, Table 2 shows the analysis of some frameworks for cloud migration decision-making.

Additionally, an organisation that intends to migrate its workloads to the cloud needs to decide which strategy satisfies the objective of migrating. Considering the migration strategies utilised by Cisco (2022) and Gartner (2011), which were comparable because they both considered migration across cloud deployment models, but gave little attention to business aspects (Jamshidi, 2015). Chapter Three will further establish this dissertation's research problem and method.

CHAPTER 3 RESEARCH PROBLEM AND METHOD

3.1 Introduction

The research problem and method used in this dissertation will be discussed in this chapter. There is a logical flow to this chapter. The opening section of the chapter highlights the dissertation's research problem. The research method is subsequently discussed in broad strokes to provide an overview of the actions taken to carry out the research. This dissertation's research approach can be replicated by other scholars, so long as they follow the same steps. A thorough explanation of the research method will be utilised to analyse the problem in the chapter that follows.

3.2 Research Problem Summary

The research problem associated with this dissertation is the absence of a standardised framework for moving on-premises workloads to the cloud. It is evident from the many Cloud migration processes that there is no universal framework for moving workloads/applications to the cloud from on-premises infrastructure (Mushi, 2020). We have a number of cloud service providers. However, for this dissertation, we would be using the Gartner (2021) Magic Quadrant for cloud infrastructure and platform services to pick on only service providers that are leaders. The reason for the selection is because they are very extensive in terms of ability to execute, completeness of vision, infrastructure and services. Figure 5 gives a clear picture of the quadrant.

Figure 5: The Magic Quadrant for Cloud Service Providers (Gartner, 2021).

Furthermore, Figure 5 shows that cloud service provider in the leaders' quadrant like Amazon offers guidelines for moving particular workload/applications to the AWS Cloud in a set of publications referred to as the AWS Prescriptive Guidance (AWS Prescriptive Guidance, 2022). For Microsoft, we have the Microsoft Cloud Adoption Framework for Azure (Microsoft, 2022) and Google Cloud Adoption Framework (Google Cloud, 2022). RedHat (RedHat, 2022), IBM (IBM, 2022) and other CSPs in the niche players or visionaries quadrant also take the same path by offering guidance on transferring particular workloads/applications to respective Cloud hosting. However, these cloud service provider's frameworks do not provide a comprehensive Cloud adoption strategy across multiple platforms. This gap creates limitations with having a seamless and clear understanding of Cloud migration. In other to further reaffirm this gap, Table 3 gives clear-cut comparison of CSPs in the leaders' quadrant of the magic quadrant in terms of market share, services and cost (Andriy, 2021).

Organisations intending to move their workload or applications to the cloud must adhere to specific migration rules established by public cloud service providers, resulting in debates over the ideal migration procedure. As a result, a Cloud migration procedure that does not rely on a specific approach developed by a Cloud Service Provider is required. In order to close up this research gap, the Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF) has been developed. This migration framework will need to meet the following set of requirements.

- Give detailed criteria for choosing which applications should be moved to the Cloud.
- Give explicit justifications and reasons for migration to specified CSPs and Services
- Establish precise standards for choosing the best migration strategy depending on the application.
- The framework should fit into the needs of small and medium businesses across various industries.

In order to satisfy the requirements outlined above, the framework will provide a holistic strategy for moving on-premises workloads/applications to the Cloud. The comprehensive approach given to the development of the framework makes it the first of its kind to further address the migration approach at the service delivery level. This makes the framework an outstanding one for closing up the research gap that was discovered.

Table 4: Compares CSPs in the leaders' quadrant of Gartner's magic quadrant.

CSPs	Market Share	Services/Migration Framework	Cost
AWS	Canalys (2020) says Amazon leads IaaS with 31% of the cloud market. Financial results for 2020 have surpassed expectations. In 2020, AWS claimed \$45 billion in revenue, 30% more than in 2019.	AWS has more than 175 cloud services that can be used in variety of ways. Amazon EC2, Amazon S3, Amazon RDS, Amazon Glacier and Amazon CloudFront are the most popular services (Andriy, 2021). The migration framework is the AWS Prescriptive Guidance (2022).	AWS costs are pay-as-you-go based on software, hardware and networking choices. Subscribers can buy a virtual AWS PC or cluster. Amazon secures subscribed systems.
AZURE	Canalys (2020) claims that Microsoft Azure's IaaS market share is 20%. In Q2 2021 revenue grew 50% from the previous quarter to \$17 billion. In Q2 2021 financial report shows that demand has risen to 34% annually.	Azure has 600+ services. Azure's IaaS includes VMs, Active Directory synchronisation, and single sign-on. The company offers mobile interaction using various solutions. The migration framework is Microsoft Cloud Adoption Framework for Azure (Microsoft, 2022).	AWS and Azure cost similarly. In some cases, Azure is less expensive than AWS. But Google Cloud is cheaper than AWS and Azure. There is no consistency across cloud providers; no two offer the same price.
GCP	Google Cloud's IaaS market share is 7% (Canalys, 2022). Google invested extensively in sales employees in 2020, resulting in a \$5 billion loss and \$13 billion in revenue.	Google Cloud offers 100 products in six categories: compute, big data, storage, networking, machine learning and databases (Andriy, 2021). The migration framework is Google Cloud Adoption Framework (Google Cloud, 2022)	Google Cloud provides a pay-per-use option. A pricing calculator and customised estimates can assist in determining costs based on locations, workloads, and other factors.

3.3 Research Methodology

The research method for this dissertation is built on the Design Science Research (DSR) method, which was written and published by Vaishnavi et al. (2004). DSR is widely used to develop innovative or new artefacts within information systems. According to Vaishnavi et al. (2004), DSR is a collection of analytic and synthetic approaches to research that aim to advance both the existing level of performance and the body of understanding within the area of research. DSR typically includes an examination of how these artefacts are used and performed in order to better understand certain aspects of the subject matter (Vaishnavi and Kuechler, 2004; Weber, 2012). Furthermore, Hevner and Wickramasinghe (2018) classified design artefacts into four categories, namely constructs, models, methods, and instantiations. These classifications can take shape in computer/human interface, algorithms, design approach, and language.

As earlier classified, the artefact can be developed based on any of the four categories, taking into great recognition the research gap that was identified (Hevner and Wickramasinghe, 2018). DSR can be categorised as a type of mixed methodologies research because it comprises both qualitative and quantitative research components and can be used with a variety of design approaches.

Table 5: Comparison of DSR to positivist and interpretive paradigms (Vaishnavi et al., 2004; Mdletshe et al., 2021).

Research Philosophy	Basic Belief			
	Ontology	Epistemology	Methodology	Axiology
Positivist	A singular reality that is knowable and probabilistic	Dispassionate; objective. Truth observer who is detached.	Quantitative and statistical observation.	Truth: beautiful and universal; prediction.
Interpretive	Multiple socially generated realities	Interactions between researcher and participant are subjective, i.e. values and knowledge.	Participant; qualitative. Hermeneutic, dialectic	Understanding: where things are and what they are.
DSR	Alternative world-states in various contexts. Socio-technological capabilities	Knowing by doing: objectively limited development within a perspective.	Developmental - Evaluate the effects of artefacts on the overall system.	Control, innovation, improvement, and comprehension.

Additionally, given the exploratory nature of DSR, it offers the chance to create an instrument that can be assessed or evaluated and allows data to be obtained a piece at a time. The main benefit of the DSR methodology, according to Weber (2012), is how it incorporates the advantages of several paradigms through the evaluation phase that could be actualised in either a positivistic, technical or interpretative way.

Considering the fundamental ideologies of ontology, epistemology, methodology and axiology paradigm, Table 5 shows how Vaishnavi et al. (2004) compared DSR to positivist (quantitative) and interpretive (qualitative) paradigms. The essential factor that DSR addressed is developing new knowledge through designing and analysing how artefacts are used (Vaishnavi et al., 2004). The DSR approach is divided into phases, each with its own output. Table 6 shows the structure, stages and outcome of each phase as it relates to this dissertation.

Table 6: The various stages of the dissertation using the design science research methodology

Stages	Objectives	Outcome
1	Identification of the Problem	Using the literature review to justify the absence of a comprehensive strategy for moving on-premises workloads to the cloud.
2	Objectives of the solution	A framework to help decision-makers move on-premises workloads to the Cloud
3	Artefact Development	The development of a Comprehensive cloud computing Framework (CCMF).
4	Demonstration	Implement a cloud migration using the comprehensive cloud migration framework (CCMF).
5	Artefact Evaluation	A naturalistic evaluation of the CCMF's efficacy, using the Framework for Evaluation in Design Science (FEDS). After the artefact demonstration, data will be gathered through interview questions. A narrative format for data analysis will be used.
6	Conclusion	Communicate the research findings to academics and practising professionals.

Furthermore, Venable and Baskerville (2012) assert that the end result of a DSR project is always an artefact that serves a specific purpose. This artefact "can be a product or a process; it

can be a technology, a tool, a methodology, a technique, a procedure, a combination of any of these, or any other means for achieving some purpose" (Venable and Baskerville, 2012). The goal of this exploratory DSR research was to design, implement, and test a decision-making framework (CCMF) for organisations intending to migrate their application/workload to the cloud. Furthermore, in view of the study's aims and objectives, the DSR approach was deemed the most suitable. This methodology is not frequently utilised, so the researcher needed to be familiar with it in order to use it. The academic ethics committee of the institution gave its approval for the study to proceed. Respect for autonomy, non-maleficence, beneficence, and justice—the four guiding ethical principles—were utilised throughout the research (Dhai and McQuoid-Mason, 2010).

In the next chapter, we will use the DSR approach to analyse further the problems and improvements needed within this dissertation.

CHAPTER 4 ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEM/SOLUTION

4.1 Introduction

The research problem associated with this dissertation is the absence of a standardised framework for moving on-premises workloads to the cloud. It is evident from the many Cloud migration processes that there is no universal framework for moving applications to the cloud from on-premises infrastructure (Mushi, 2020). To adequately analyse this problem, we will further break it down using the DSR method, which involves developing new knowledge through designing and analysing how artefacts are used (Vaishnavi et al., 2004).

4.2 Stage 1: Identification of the Problem

Identifying a research problem can originate from several diverse perspectives, such as advances in industry or discovering issues within a particular field (Vaishnavi et al., 2019). A review of the literature on cloud computing migration was presented in Chapter 2. It explains the issue around the absence of a comprehensive cloud migration framework. An analysis of studies from professionals, scholars and researchers was done as part of the literature review to pinpoint the major problems with transitioning to the cloud. The literature review is approached by systematically searching related articles from Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore and Staffordshire University Libraries databases. Google Scholar offers research articles for scholars and researchers. At the same time, the Staffordshire University Libraries repository (Staffordshire University Libraries, 2022), IEEE Xplore and other academic open libraries feature more academic research papers.

4.3 Stage 2: Objectives of the solution

The objective of the solution is a detailed proposal which is developed from an understanding of the issue (Vaishnavi et al., 2004). New functionality is considered a creative move (Vaishnavi et al., 2004). This dissertation will address the lack of a holistic method for moving on-premise workloads/applications to the cloud. The researcher's goal in writing this dissertation is to develop a comprehensive framework for organisations/businesses to use when deciding whether or not to migrate to the Cloud. The framework developed in this dissertation will serve as the artefact.

4.4 Stage 3: Artefact Development

The artefact, the Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework, is developed in the third stage. The development is actualised in various building blocks. These building blocks, which will be

a tool for making the decisions in response to specific inquiries, will be put into a workflow to assist individuals in making cloud migration decisions. These blocks are labelled Phase I to IV.

Phase I begins the framework process, establishing whether or not a particular application or workload needs to be hosted in the cloud or the on-premises infrastructure. Clear eligibility criteria for cloud migration will be based on maintenance, availability and reliability. The output from Phase I, which will be a precise classification of where the application or workload would be hosted, will serve as an input for the next phase.

Phase II addresses how beneficial an organisation migrating to the cloud would be. For this to be determined, we will adopt a tried-and-trusted framework to help decision-makers figure out if moving to the cloud is an excellent strategic move. We have several frameworks for actualising this, such as systemic scorecard, performance pyramid, Tableau de Bord and Balance Scorecard. For the purpose of this research and reviewed literature, the Balanced Scorecard framework was selected as the best approach to assessing an organisation's value for Phase II. The Input for this phase is the eligible workloads/applications that can be hosted in the cloud. The output will be a collection of services that will be utilised for migration.

Phase III determines how prepared an organisation is for cloud migration. The readiness of an organisation is a vital part of a successful migration. In this phase, criteria developed from the literature review are used to focus on things to look out for in other to see if an organisation is ready for cloud migration. This organisational readiness check will cut across both business and technical areas.

Phase IV is structured to seamlessly enable various organisational workloads or applications to migrate to the cloud. In other to achieve a successful migration to the cloud, the proper migration strategy and service delivery model must be implemented. As earlier reviewed in the literature, we have three main service delivery models: SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS. After that, a further breakdown of the right migration approach for each service delivery. The approach can either be re-host for IaaS, refactor for PaaS, revise for IaaS/PaaS, rebuild for PaaS and replace for SaaS.

4.5 Stage 4: Demonstration

The demonstration stage involves the implementation of cloud migration using the comprehensive cloud migration framework (CCMF). This implementation will use a cloud service provider, which the developed migration framework will suggest as best for such an application/workload. The demonstration is a migration use case that shows the decision-

making process and viability of moving one of an organisation's main infrastructures (on-premises storage) to the cloud. The case study will be demonstrated utilising the steps proposed by Hancock, Algozzine and Lim (2021).

4.6 Stage 5: Artefact Evaluation

The artefact evaluation stage, where the efficacy of the CCMF is checked to see if it answers the questions raised about cloud migration. Furthermore, this dissertation output aims to make decisions on whether and how to migrate workloads or applications from on-premises to the cloud. In the DSR evaluation process, the artefact is assessed based on its primary goal, capacity to address challenges or advance technology, usability, impact (including any potential drawbacks), and functionality (Baskerville et al., 2016). Various frameworks can be utilised within the DSR scenario to evaluate the developed artefact (Sonnenberg and vom Brocke, 2012; Venable, Pries-Heje and Baskerville, 2012). However, Jarvinen (2007) argues that the utility criterion is overemphasised in the evaluation phase of DSR and that DSR should not just focus on producing an artefact which functions "properly" at the time it is developed. Instead, it should take into account novel possibilities for design and research as those are what may have greater relevance and value for the economy. The DSR ontology and epistemology provide backing for the idea that the produced artefact need not be compared to a standard but instead evaluated against the set requirement/specifications (Cleven, Gubler and Hüner, 2009). For this research, the migration framework (artefact) must meet the following requirements.

- Give detailed criteria for choosing which applications should be moved to the Cloud.
- Give explicit justifications and reasons for migration to specified CSPs and Services
- Establish precise standards for choosing the best migration strategy depending on the application.
- The framework should fit into the needs of small and medium businesses across various industries.

The evaluation will be done using an improved Framework for Evaluation in Design Science (FEDS). The evaluation will be formative. This is utilised to enhance the qualities and efficiency of the artefact. The evaluation method will be a naturalistic evaluation, which investigates how the artefact performs in a real-life scenario using a case study implementation (Baskerville et al., 2016).

For a successful evaluation of the artefact, data collection plays a vital role. An adaptive case study will be employed as an artefact demonstration for gathering data. Data will be gathered via interviews following the artefact demonstration. Furthermore, to ensure that no data is lost

during analysis, the interviews will be stored on a smartphone, laptop, or voice recorder. The questions which will be asked during the interview were developed from the set of requirements that the framework needs to actualise. The responses to this interview will help evaluate if the artefact provides a clear solution to the research problem. The interview questions are outlined below;

- Is the CCMF considered a comprehensive model for making cloud migration decisions?
- Will the CCMF be applicable to every Cloud migration decision?
- When making decisions, does the CCMF consider anything else besides cost?
- What additional aspects must be considered before making decisions while using CCMF?
- Is the CCMF leading to a better grasp of the challenges involved in decision-making?
- Is the CCMF explicit and detailed on the steps to take?
- Is it simple to understand the CCMF procedure?
- Is implementing CCMF easy without guidance?
- Is anything in the CCMF unnecessary?
- What CCMF aspect is not necessary for the cloud migration decision-making process?
- What modifications to the CCMF would you propose?
- Does CCMF require any further features to make it more comprehensive?

Furthermore, It is reasonable to assume that there will be improvement opportunities given that this will be the framework's first testing and evaluation. The final four questions are intended to prompt improvements to the framework from research participants with Cloud migration experience. Each phase of the CCMF is illustrated in the case study using a prototype migration and a structured presentation of the CCMF.

4.7 Stage 6: Conclusion

The conclusion of this dissertation will remind the readers of the statement of the problem, the aims of the study, and the criteria needed to address the migration decision-making issues. Solving the issue will only be possible if a solution meets all of the specified requirements in section 3.2 and the objectives of this dissertation, as stated in section 1.6. The evaluation findings and the manner in which the study's goals were attained will be provided by the researcher after data analysis has been done.

4.8 Ethical Considerations

The individuals and companies involved in this research will be treated confidentially. To safeguard the respondents' identities, we will be referring to the companies as company A, and the individuals as respondent A, respondent B, Respondent C, and Respondent D. Participants in the study will be given a research participation document with anonymity guaranteed.

Each participant will fill out and grant permission, which will grant consent to use the data gathered from them. Before granting consent, a detailed information sheet will be handed out to the participant informing them of the research objectives, the reason for their selection, their freedom to opt out, and how well their confidentiality and privacy is being ensured. Hancock and Algozzine (2016) gave practical guidelines for carrying out a case study, which was very useful to the research. Every respondent gave insightful feedback on the CCMF. Furthermore, the collected data were analysed to reflect each and every individual's contributions. The interview made respondents contribute in greater detail, which made it easier to present the findings of the evaluation narratively.

CHAPTER 5 DESIGN OF ARTEFACT

5.1 Introduction

The framework proposed in this dissertation is developed to solve the issues associated with the absence of a standardised framework for moving on-premises workloads to the cloud. It is vital to note that addressing this issue will only be possible if a solution meets all of the specified requirements in section 3.2 and the objectives of this dissertation, as stated in section 1.6. The CCMF is developed to give organisations a framework for making decisions which can be used for any cloud migration project. This chapter's deliverable is a fully developed decision framework, which will be evaluated in the next chapter.

5.2 Overview of the Design Process

As discussed in section 4.4, this dissertation's requirement has been streamlined to guide the development of the artefact. These requirements are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Requirements for Framework Design

The requirements for the framework design, as shown in Figure 6, were developed to address specific design questions during the framework development. Each requirement has been named RFD1, RFD2, RFD3 and RFD4. RFD1 ensures that organisations have a clear way to figure out which on-premise applications/workloads can be moved to the Cloud. RFD 2 gives organisations a way to figure out why they need to move to the Cloud by examining the

advantages of migrating. This ensures that every application/workload passes through a benefit evaluation process. The goal of RFD 3 is to ensure organisations use the appropriate migration technique for every given application/workload because different applications/workloads will call for varying migration strategies. RFD 4 ensures the framework is replicable for each migration and applicable to every organisation.

Using the DSR approach, we took into account the fact that the framework will require various decision-making phases. These phases are actualised in various building blocks, which will be a tool for making decisions in response to specific inquiries. The various phases will be put into a workflow to assist individuals in making cloud migration decisions. These blocks are labelled Phase I to IV. Each phase will have an Input, Process and Output substructure, as shown in Figure 7. The first and second stages of this dissertation have been discussed within chapter 1 and most of chapter 2. The artefact - Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework, is developed in the third stage.

Figure 7: Phase-by-phase substructure

5.2.1 Phase I – Migration Eligibility Check

Phase I begins the framework process, as shown in Figure 8. According to Binz et al. (2014), a migration strategy starts with a procedure that establishes which applications are Cloud-eligible. This strategy involves establishing whether or not a particular application or workload needs to be hosted in the cloud or the on-premises infrastructure. The application/workloads will be assessed in accordance with the organisation's specific standards and procedures. In order to initiate this phase, the organisation's application/workload inventory will be used to choose the applications to be considered for migration. The application /workload inventory contains a list of all applications used within an organisation. After the selection, applications/workload will be checked to know if it is eligible for cloud migration. Clear eligibility attributes for cloud migration will be based on maintenance, availability and reliability (Kaur, Pandey and Singh, 2018). These attributes, which were further explained and implemented by Mushi (2020), evaluate how dependable these applications are, based on the organisation's goals. The tool used to check for eligibility is the RAM paradigm that is widely employed in the field of science

research. By reusing an already established tool, we can absolutely guarantee that it will provide accurate results inside the framework. The output from Phase I, will be a precise classification of where the application or workload would be hosted, which will serve as an input for the next phase.

Figure 8: Phase I - Checking if Application/workload is Eligible for cloud migration

5.2.2 Phase II – Value Evaluation

Phase II addresses how beneficial an organisation’s migration to the cloud would be. Identifying the benefit Technology contributes to the organisation is the initial stage in the design process. According to Nayar and Kumar (2018), the importance of technology to an organisation will help determine the benefit of transferring an application to the cloud from on-premises. For this to be determined, we will adopt a tried-and-trusted framework to help decision-makers figure out if moving to the cloud is an excellent strategic move. We have several frameworks for actualising this, such as systemic scorecard, performance pyramid, Tableau de Bord and Balance Scorecard (Beck, Reck and Siegfried, 2022). For the purpose of this research and reviewed literature, the Balanced Scorecard framework was selected as the best approach to assessing an organisation's value for Phase II.

Figure 9: Phase II – Shows the Value Evaluation process using the BSC Framework

Kaplan and Norton (1992) created the Balanced Scorecard (BSC), which takes a four-pronged approach to analyse the performance of an organisation. This approach uses three non-financial performance metrics from the four: internal business process perspective, customer perspective,

learning and growth perspective, and financial measure (Omollo, 2015; Mushi, 2020). Every viewpoint serves a particular objective (Kaplan and Norton, 1992). Wongrassamee et al. (2003) state that due to the unique features and various approaches of each organisation, the BSC cannot be used generically. Instead, every organisation will have its own performance metrics that are ideal for its organisational effectiveness. In order to fully adopt the Balanced Scorecard, the four perspectives should be considered by organisations as being interconnected.

5.2.2.1 Using BSC within the framework

BSC was chosen because it incorporates a broad range of variables when evaluating the commercial potential of cloud migration. Therefore, BSC will be utilised to assess value spanning organisational procedures, development and learning, customers, and finances in the proposed framework. The BSC will need to be implemented by experts in those fields. For instance, a finance expert would be needed to examine the financial components' investment return. The same applies to the customer service department analysing how well customers derive value for services rendered, which also applies to the business, development and learning areas. The BSC can be used to determine whether or not the migration of a certain application will yield a positive return on investment.

As shown in Figure 9, the Input for this phase is the eligible workloads/applications that can be hosted in the cloud, and the output will be a collection of services that will be utilised for migration.

5.2.3 Phase III – Organisation’s Readiness Check

The term "readiness" in this phase refers to a decision-making process based on risk, enabling a company to move its applications to the Cloud effectively and ensuring that the CSP will be able to meet the company's migration needs (Kundra, 2011). Therefore, both internal and external checks of readiness are necessary. Also, part of being ready for the cloud is being able to handle its intricacies and security.

Figure 10: Phase III – Shows the Readiness Check process of the Organisation

Furthermore, by using Loebbecke et al. (2011)'s "magic matrices" for cloud readiness assessment, we would be able to evaluate an organisation's readiness. The metrics provided by Loebbecke et al. (2011) for Cloud readiness are; Significance to the main business, Availability, standardisation of IT services, administration and management of the application, networking capabilities, identity management, and compliance with the law. Furthermore, Alharbi, Atkins and Stanier (2017) stated that IT services that were evaluated using this approach were divided into three groups: (1) cloud-ready, (2) not cloud-ready, and (3) cloud-ready in the next years. The readiness of an organisation is a vital part of a successful migration. In this phase, criteria developed from the literature review and Loebbecke et al. (2011)'s "magic matrices" for cloud readiness assessment are used to focus on things to look out for in other to see if an organisation is ready for cloud migration. This organisation's readiness check will cut across both business and technical areas. Figure 10 illustrates the structure of the process.

5.2.4 Phase IV – Migration Strategy Selection

The type of application or workload plays a vital role in deciding which migration approach is best. The output from phase III, a more defined recommendation of applications and services for migration, will be the input for the final phase. Furthermore, the output will be a document containing the selected strategy and plan for migration. Figure 11 further explains the phase's input, process and output stages.

Figure 11: Phase IV – Shows the migration strategy selection process

Furthermore, to achieve a successful migration to the cloud, the proper migration strategy and service delivery model must be implemented. As earlier reviewed in the literature, we have three main service delivery models: SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS (Chen, 2020). Furthermore, (Ahmad, Naveed and Hoda, 2018) suggest that it is important to follow a well-planned strategy while making decisions and carrying out migrations. Considering the six cloud migration strategies outlined by Stephen (2016) shown in figure 12, which are the 6 R's namely; Rehosting, Replatform, Repurchase, Refactoring, Retire and Retain. The re-host strategy basically uses the IaaS service model to host the existing applications on the cloud platform.

Figure 12: Shows the cloud migration strategies (Stephen, 2016).

Re-platform migration approach uses the implementation of changes to the PaaS service paradigm to optimise the host application platform. Repurchase approach enables the acquisition of new SaaS-based solutions. The refactoring approach would necessitate that the services be redeveloped using cloud-native functionalities. In some circumstances, it could be a good idea to retain some services for the on-site infrastructure. In such cases, the retain approach is used. While in other instances, some applications and services may no longer be useful, so they should be retired (Ahmad, Naveed and Hoda, 2018).

Numerous factors must be considered when choosing the migration approach and service. Whether an application is migrated by rehosting to IaaS, refactoring, refactoring, or repurchasing SaaS depends on how much effort it will take to make it work in the Cloud. The length of time it takes to migrate an application or workload to the cloud depends on how complex it is. However, at this point, the organisation will begin developing plans over which strategy and method to adopt.

5.2.5 Putting Together the Framework

So far, the phases of the framework have only been discussed separately. The first phase, as shown in figure 8, addresses the issues around workload/application that can be migrated to the cloud, which was the requirement labelled RFD 1. Moreover, the second phase, which further addressed the benefits of cloud migration to organisations, justifies the requirement labelled RFD 2, which is the requirement for a business performance indicator. The third phase also

further looks into the readiness of the organisation both internally and externally, using the “magic metric” for assessment. This phase repositions the organisation to see if it is cloud-ready, not cloud-ready, or cloud-ready in the next years. This helps further define the best migrations approach required in RFD 3. The final phase, which takes place only when phases I-III are satisfactorily addressed, will output a final documentation which will be the plan and strategy for seamless cloud migration. This stage meets the RFD 4 requirement by clearly showing how flexible and applicable the framework is to every industry. Figure 13 depicts the finalise Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF). All phases have been put together to have a standard structure for the framework.

Figure 13: The Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF)

CHAPTER 6 IMPLEMENTATION OF ARTEFACT

6.1 Introduction

The demonstration stage of this dissertation involves the implementation of cloud migration using the comprehensive cloud migration framework (CCMF). This implementation will use a cloud service provider, which the migration framework that is developed will suggest as best for such an application. The demonstration is a migration use case that shows the decision-making process and viability of moving one of an organisation's main infrastructures (on-premises storage) to the cloud. The case study will be demonstrated utilising the steps proposed by Hancock, Algozzine and Lim (2021), which are; setting the stage, determining what we know, selecting a framework, and gathering information from interviews.

In other to successfully implement the artefact, the initial step of setting up the stage has been covered in chapter 5, where the framework was developed. Furthermore, the case study approach to this implementation is the determinant of what we know, and the CCMF has been the selected framework for migration. The aspect of getting data from interviews is looked into in detail in chapter 7, where the framework is evaluated.

6.2 Proposed Migration Case Study

The case study is an organisation which provides IT solutions to several organisations. The organisation named company A has its office in the UK. The use case in “company A” is the possibility of migrating one of the organisation’s storage facilities to the cloud. The organisation manages several public car parks monitored by smart cameras. These cameras automatically capture licence plate data from every car that enters and exits every car park and send the data to a storage infrastructure on-premises, as shown in figure 14.

Figure 14: Shows the smart camera capturing information and sending it to on-prem storage.

Storage plays a vital role in the safety of the data captured by the cameras, and scaling up physical storage infrastructure is starting to be a challenge. Due to how this could impact the services the organisation renders, it has become very necessary to explore solutions which will be exceptionally affordable, highly available, durable and secure.

6.3 CCMF Implementation Using Case Study

The CCMF will be used to assist company A in the decision-making process over the best cloud migration option and services. This will be addressed within the implementation at the various phases of the CCMF. Company A was reached to gather all necessary information needed to adequately examine and address the problem they are encountering. As earlier seen in chapter 5, the CCMF has four phases which we will go through in order to have a seamless migration to the cloud.

6.3.1 Phase I – Migration Eligibility Check

Phase I begins the framework process, as shown in Figure 8. According to Binz et al. (2014), a migration strategy starts with a procedure that establishes which applications are Cloud-eligible. From the information gathered from Company A, the major challenge they indicated was storage. Therefore, given the service which needs migration, we need to establish if the kind of storage they maintain is cloud-eligible. The question which needs answers is if the on-premise infrastructure satisfies the eligibility attributes for cloud migration. This will be based on maintenance, availability and reliability, as indicated by Kaur, Pandey and Singh, (2018). If the on-premises infrastructure provides the above attributes, it is not eligible for cloud migration. Has indicated in the information gathered from company A, maintenance is becoming an issue due to the increasing demand for storage. Availability and reliability cannot be promised because continuous maintenance cannot be guaranteed. This makes the storage infrastructure of company A cloud eligible. In order to further evaluate how beneficial migrating company A's storage infrastructure to the cloud can be, we will be updating phase II of the CCMF with the application (storage) which is eligible for migration to the cloud.

6.3.2 Phase II – Value Evaluation

Phase II addresses how beneficial company A's migration to the cloud would be. Identifying the benefit Technology contributes to company A is the initial stage of this phase. One important aspect which company A indicate concern is the ability of the cloud solution to be exceptionally affordable, highly available, durable and secure. These are the key benefit which company A envisages as value for migrating their storage infrastructure to the cloud. According to Nayar

and Kumar (2018), the importance of technology to an organisation will help determine the benefit of transferring an application to the cloud from on-premises. CCMF proposes the use of the Balance Scorecard framework for assessing these values. The balance scorecard framework evaluates values from the standpoint of four key perspectives, which are organisational procedures, development and learning, customers' standpoint, and finances.

From the information gathered from company A, the on-premises storage infrastructure, which costs £19,500, is made up of two workstations, with each having 64GB RAM, 20TB of effective storage, running on windows server 2008, a tape drive, rack, and network devices. Also, company A has a system support engineer who is paid £45,000 per year and recurrent maintenance expenditure of £4000 per year. For company A, the total infrastructure cost for three years will be the sum of the cost of on-premises storage infrastructure and recurrent maintenance and support cost; $£19500 + (3 \times £4000) = £31500$. To increase the storage size of the infrastructure, it was observed that the need for an additional engineer, storage drives and increased recurrent maintenance expenditure was a huge strain on the business. Hence the need for a solution that is exceptionally affordable, highly available, durable and secure. Table 6 shows a financial comparison between company A's three major cloud provider options and the on-premises storage infrastructure.

Table 7: Shows a comparison of company A and cloud providers' storage infrastructure costs.

On-Premises and Cloud Service Providers Storage (20TB)	Duration/Cost			References
	1 Month	1 Year	3 Year	
Company A	£875	£10500	£31500	
Amazon Simple Storage Service	£417.03	£5004.36	£15013.08	(Amazon, 2022)
Azure - Blob Storage	£524	£6288	£18864	(Azure, 2022)
Google Cloud Storage	£460	£5520	£16560	(Google Cloud, 2022)

Comparing company A's storage infrastructure cost to any cloud service provider's storage applications is very expensive and unsustainable. Also, considering the necessity for an expansion of storage capacity. Migration to Amazon Simple storage is the cheapest option if affordability is the main factor. The expectation of company A closely aligns with the values the balanced scorecard seeks. The BSC values centre around the customer, finance, organisational procedures, development and learning. This is a true reflection of the need for an exceptionally affordable solution in terms of finance, availability in business procedures,

durability and security from a customer standpoint. According to Bignall (2021), the benefits of moving cloud-eligible infrastructure to the cloud are; significant cost savings, more rapid service rollouts, Secured data storage, and encouraged collaboration regardless of the business location. The maintenance is handled by the cloud service provider. This benefits answers questions mostly about how efficient and valuable the three cloud service providers are compared in Table 4. Gartner’s (2021) Magic Quadrant for cloud infrastructure and platform services addresses them as leaders due to their high level of completeness of vision and ability to execute.

6.3.3 Phase III – Organisation’s Readiness Check

This phase checks the level of readiness company A possesses. This check looks for risks associated with moving the on-premises storage infrastructure to the cloud against the CSP’s ability to meet the company’s needs (Kundra, 2011). Therefore, internal and external readiness checks are necessary to verify that the migration process can handle intricacies and security. Has proposed by the CCMF, we would be using Loebbecke et al. (2011)’s “magic matrices” and Alharbi et al. (2017) IT Service evaluation approach for cloud readiness assessment. An overview of the assessment is shown in Table 7, based on the information gathered from company A.

Table 8: Shows the Cloud Readiness Assessment for Company A’s Storage Migration

Metrics	High	Low
Significance to the main business	✓	
Availability	✓	
standardisation	✓	
administration and management	✓	
networking capabilities		✓
identity management	✓	
compliance	✓	

The readiness of an organisation is a vital part of a successful migration. In this phase, criteria developed from the literature review and Loebbecke et al. (2011)’s “magic matrices” for cloud readiness assessment are used to focus on things to look out for in other to see if an organisation

is ready for cloud migration. This organisation's readiness check will cut across both business and technical areas. Has shown in Table 7, the significance of IT services to company A is High, and with such shown, it is cloud ready. Availability is also high, which shows how critical the storage infrastructure is to company A, which makes it most likely ready for cloud migration. Standardisation with company A's IT services is of a high rating, which also positions the company in a cloud-ready position. Administration and management play a vital role in ensuring that company A is cloud-ready, and the rating shows it has a high level of administration and management. In terms of the networking capability of the storage infrastructure, it is rated as low, which indicates the need for a more robust network infrastructure, which migration to the cloud is expected to handle. This is not a setback for cloud readiness but a need which meets the readiness for cloud migration. The management of identity with company A's infrastructure is rated as high as data stored on-premises is highly secured at all times. Moreover, the same security requirement is being reemphasised for the cloud infrastructure. Compliance with regulatory and legal requirements indicates that company A is cloud-ready. A high rating for compliance is a positive indication of being ready to migrate to the cloud.

6.3.4 Phase IV – Migration Strategy Selection

The output from phase III is a more defined recommendation of applications and services for migration. To select the appropriate migration strategy, the type of application or workload plays a vital role in deciding which migration approach is best. We have recommendations for CSPs like AWS, Azure, and GCP at this stage. For company A, having a cloud service that is exceptionally affordable, highly available, durable and secured has become very necessary. The proper migration strategy and service delivery model must be implemented to achieve a successful migration to the cloud. As earlier reviewed in the literature, we have three main service delivery models: SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS (Chen, 2020). The storage infrastructure for smart/IoT devices in the cloud will run most efficiently on an Infrastructure as a service delivery model. IaaS offers a model where the cloud service provider is in charge of purchasing, maintaining and upgrading the infrastructure. Even though company A does not control or manage services like the firewall, which was previously part of the network infrastructure, it can manage resources such as storage, operating system and applications which have been deployed. A notable advantage of IaaS is that the CSP utilises cutting-edge technology, enabling company A to have a much more improved service delivery time.

Furthermore, a migration strategy proposed by CCMF is the 6 R's" namely; Rehosting, Replatform, Repurchase, Refactoring, Retire and Retain. Company A's scenario clearly requires a rehost migration strategy, which is often referred to as the lift and shift technique. It entails moving a replica of company A's current storage infrastructure to the cloud. The time it takes to migrate an application or workload to the cloud depends on its complexity. However, at this point, company A will begin developing plans to best migrate based on the strategy and method already established. The plan will entail using IaaS as the service delivery model and Amazon Simple Storage Service (20TB) as the service to utilise for this migration.

6.3.5 Implementation using the CCMF Migration Decisions

Furthermore, to finalise the implementation of the CCMF, the migration of the storage infrastructure from on-premises to AWS will be actualised. Figure 15 shows how the infrastructure looks in the AWS cloud environment.

Figure 15: Shows the Topology of storage migration from On-Premises to Aws Cloud.

In addition to Amazon Simple Storage Service, AWS offers some free services that come on as default to setting up your workload in the cloud. One essential service company A will need to migrate data from its on-premises storage to the cloud is the AWS Transfer Family service.

AWS Transfer Family allows seamless transfer of unstructured data to the Amazon Simple Storage Service. The Amazon S3 also has free 5GB of standard storage for 12 months. This service is exceptional because we have the private VPC endpoint, which transfers data within networks that are internal and can be more secure. Screenshots of various stages of the migration process are shown below. These screenshots include the set-up of Amazon Simple Storage Service, Amazon Transfer Family, Amazon Elastic File System (EFS) and Direct Connect.

Figure 16: Shows the successful creation of the S3 Storage bucket for Company A.

The Amazon simple storage service is where all the data captured by the smart camera will be stored. As shown in Figure 15, the creation of AWS's storage space was seamless without putting any physical infrastructure together. We just specified the name we want to give the

Figure 17: Shows the AWS Transfer Family Server Created

storage and select the options for either making it public or private. For security reasons, Company A cannot be accessible publicly. Figure 16 shows the creation of the transfer family server for recurring file transfers from on-premises to the cloud. In a situation where company A decides not to decommission its on-premises infrastructure, it is important that the transfer of data across infrastructures should be flexible. This service plays a vital role in actualising this flexibility, using either the FTP, FTPS, ASC2 or SFTP protocols.

Figure 18: Shows the Creation of the Elastic File System

The creation of the elastic file system shown in Figure 17 enables a service that ultimately manages workloads that require a shared file system like NFS. This service is very durable, available, secured, compliant and most importantly, it is scalable.

Figure 19: Shows the Creation of the Connection to On-premises from Direct Connect

As shown in Figure 18, AWS direct connect service establishes a secure connection between the on-premises infrastructure and AWS cloud infrastructure. This service allows company A workloads which require reduced latency or high bandwidth to connect to AWS via a high throughput, secured, and private AWS network.

In summary, the implementation of this migration using the CCMF has been able to offer company A an affordable, highly available, durable and secured solution to the challenge of scaling up on-premise storage infrastructure.

CHAPTER 7 EVALUATION OF ARTEFACT

7.1 Introduction

In Chapter six, we implemented the use of the CCMF by assisting Company A in the decision-making process, which further led to the successful implementation of migrating on-premises storage infrastructure to the cloud. This chapter aims to assess the CCMF's effectiveness in resolving the research problem by comparing it to the requirements specified in section 3.2. The evaluation of the CCMF was done by professionals of organisations that frequently make decisions regarding cloud migration.

Organisations considering moving their on-premises infrastructure/workload must select from several migration strategies. The different strategies for migrating make the process more challenging because there are several choices to explore. Considering these strategies in more detail, the academic and professional communities adopt different strategies. Professionals propose solutions for migrating a particular application to a certain cloud service provider, which might not be viable for a different CSP. Consequently, this establishes that there is no standardised framework for moving on-premises applications/workloads to the cloud. Which necessitated the development of the CCMF, which was created to meet the requirements outlined below;

- Give detailed criteria for choosing which applications should be moved to the Cloud.
- Give explicit justifications and reasons for migration to specified CSPs and Services
- Establish precise standards for choosing the best migration strategy depending on the application.
- The framework should fit into the needs of small and medium businesses across various industries.

The evaluation strategy will be looked into next to understand how data was gathered and analysed.

7.2 Evaluation Strategy

The evaluation of the CCMF was done by professionals who worked in organisations where real live migration decisions often take place in order to determine its efficacy. To actualise the evaluation, we initiated the process by seeking approval from the professionals taking part in the research. This is because it involves getting data from professionals who have several years of expertise in cloud technology. The request for approval was presented as a formal letter with

the ethical approval form also attached, which shows approval from the institution to embark on this research. After the approval was granted, the collection and analysis of the data commenced.

7.3 Overview of Research Respondents

The research respondents were all professionals with over ten years of experience within the cloud technology industry. They are all presently working as experts in positions that will always require their input when making cloud migration decisions for both new and existing infrastructures. The respondents cut across various continents across the world. The respondents' cumulative years of experience will further guarantee the collection of valuable and quality data for this research. Table 8 shows the details of each respondent who was part of this research.

Table 9: Shows the details of the research respondents

Alias	Position	Cloud Related Job Description
Respondent A	Cloud Architect	Design and Selection of a solution
Respondent B	Chief Information Officer	Establish guidelines and approval
Respondent C	Head IT Operations	Influences decision-making on a solution
Respondent D	Cloud Administrator	Design and Selection of a solution

Respondent A is a Cloud Architect who is tasked with the responsibility of translating a project's technical needs into a design and structure which drives the outcome of the project. The cloud architect also connects the dot between the organisation's complicated issues and cloud-based solutions. Respondent B, the Chief information officer, is in charge of managing the organisation's new and current IT procedures, providing upgrade recommendations and granting approvals for the most effective solutions. As the Head of IT operation, Respondent C ensures that all IT operations are well budgeted and aligned with the overall IT strategic plan. Respondent D, the cloud administrator, manages the organisation's cloud infrastructure and functionality.

The respondents have been contacted to seek their consent to participate in the research. A total of nine professionals were contacted to assist in the evaluation stage. However, due to their busy schedules, we could not lay hold on them. Only four were interviewed. The interview of

each respondent lasted for one hour, where the initial 30 minutes were used to present the proposed framework, and the interview was done within the remaining 30 minutes.

7.4 The Collection and Evaluation of Data from Respondents

The collection of data was done via interview questions. The questions were asked via an audio call with the respondents. The questions have been structured in a way to address each requirement areas that was stated in section 7.1. The respondents were asked the questions below;

Question 1:

- a) Is the CCMF considered a comprehensive model for making cloud migration decisions?
- b) Will the CCMF be applicable to every Cloud migration decision?

Question 2:

- a) When making decisions, does the CCMF consider anything else besides from cost?
- b) What additional aspects must be considered before making decisions while using CCMF?

Question 3:

- a) Is the CCMF leading to a better grasp of the challenges involved in decision-making?

Question 4:

- a) Is the CCMF explicit and detailed on the steps to take?
- b) Is it simple to understand the CCMF procedure?
- c) Is implementing CCMF easy without guidance?

Question 5:

- a) Is anything in the CCMF unnecessary?
- b) What CCMF aspect is unnecessary for the cloud migration decision-making process?

Question 6:

- a) What modifications to the CCMF would you propose?
- b) Does CCMF require any further features to make it more comprehensive?

The responses for each Question have been outlined in Annexe C, and these responses will be evaluated afterwards.

7.5 Analysis of the Data

The data analysis will be done by analysing the responses of each respondent to a set of questions,

Question 1:

- a) Is the CCMF considered a comprehensive model for making cloud migration decisions?
- b) Will the CCMF be applicable to every Cloud migration decision?

All the respondents agreed that the CCMF is a very comprehensive framework and is very applicable for making cloud migration decisions. Respondent A concurs but believes that the CCMF is lacking in interoperability. Respondent A believes that when a workload or application is migrated to the cloud, interoperability between the on-premises workload /application and the cloud infrastructure is required. Furthermore proposed the inclusion of interoperability in the conditions for eligibility checks. Respondent B disagrees and is also worried about the approach. The respondent feels the evaluation of the value associated should come first. Quoting the popular saying of the comparison of business and information technology in relation to how business is driven by information technology. Respondent C gave a positive response to the framework being comprehensive. Based on his expertise in developing solutions within the cloud and also a keen advocate of capabilities within the cloud environment. Respondent C also highlights that BSC, which is the chosen framework in phase II, addresses the management of performance from a broad perspective which includes adopting a solution. Respondent D raised questions over the issues surrounding the total cost of ownership for organisations and where it will be placed in the framework.

Question 2:

- a) When making decisions, does the CCMF consider anything else besides from cost?
- b) What additional aspects must be considered before making decisions while using CCMF?

Respondent A noted that the CCMF has shown consideration for other areas aside from cost and mentioned interoperability as one of the necessary checks to be made within the framework. Respondent B indicated that the only thing which comes to mind is considering the perspective of governance and probably more about managing risk. Also, respondent B stated that the value assessment phase should be given a more in-depth approach than just the BSC. Respondent C is concerned that having the right people on board is even more critical. Furthermore, respondent C said that the framework needs to look from the angle of not just IT organisations

but also deeply into businesses intending to use cloud services. Respondent D raised the issue of regulation and compliance, giving an instance that most financial institutions will not put so critical infrastructure on a cloud platform outside their country.

Question 3:

Is the CCMF leading to a better grasp of the challenges involved in decision-making?

Respondent B says he believes the CCMF leads to a better decision-making process. Furthermore, respondent B states that although the financial impact is often a major factor, it is vital to remember that other factors also have a role. Respondent D admits that the CCMF definitely gives a clear definition of the problems faced by organisations with making the right decisions concerning cloud migration. For respondents A and D, it is also a yes to the capabilities of the CCMF to better grasp the challenges that come up during cloud migration decision-making.

Question 4:

- a) Is the CCMF explicit and detailed on the steps to take?
- b) Is it simple to understand the CCMF procedure?
- c) Is implementing CCMF easy without guidance?

Every one of the respondents concurred with the simplicity of the CCMF. According to respondent B, CCMF can be implemented without guidance but needs additional explanation before going into various phases. In addition, the respondent says a process or flow chart to navigate through can be helpful. Respondent C's input was that the process is straightforward to implement and that it clearly links technological expenditures to business objectives. Furthermore, finalised it by saying, "you do not need any help from anyone. It is simple and easy to understand." Respondent A is also considering it from the technological point of view, in which interoperability is lacking. Respondent A further says they see the assessment of the value phase look more like a corporate evaluation and ends by saying the implementation of the CCMF without guidance is a yes. For respondent D, the steps are detailed but do not look sequential.

Question 5:

- a) Is anything in the CCMF unnecessary?
- b) What CCMF aspect is unnecessary for the cloud migration decision-making process?

From respondents B and D's responses, they do not see anything or an unnecessary aspect of the decision-making process. Respondent B see all the phases as well-defined and clear. Respondent A is unsure how the growth and learning viewpoint should be implemented or where it should be placed within the framework. Suggesting it be aligned with phase III, which addresses organisational readiness. Respondent C also brought a different perspective of the two separate phases for I and II as unnecessary. Saying that the eligibility and value check phases are collapsed into one and should address decision-making per system basis.

Question 6:

- a) What modifications to the CCMF would you propose?
- b) Does CCMF require any further features to make it more comprehensive?

Respondent D proposed the consideration of the compliance and regulatory aspect of cloud migration by making sure that the appropriate regulations associated with the deployment of cloud infrastructure are employed. Respondent A raises a question on market dynamics, on whether to take the lead or follow. Respondent B suggests that the cloud migration process implementation should be done clearly, whether simultaneously or phase by phase. Moreover, consider how these changes will impact the organisations/businesses that are migrating.

7.6 Evaluation Results

Respondents A, C and D were positive about the CCMF being a comprehensive framework because it could be used to make decisions about cloud migration. Respondent B, on the other hand, was not entirely positive about the CCMF. Respondent B also agreed but argued that the framework was more of an IT approach than a business/organisation's viewpoint.

Every one of the respondents acknowledged CCMF as a framework that takes into account a wide range of cloud migration-related concerns and proposed additional ones. These proposals will aid the CCMF in becoming even more comprehensive. Some of the concerns proposed related to governance, regulations, compliance, the total cost of ownership and market dynamics.

The respondents unanimously acknowledged that the CCMF helps shed light on the problems that must be considered while deciding to move to the Cloud.

All respondents agreed that the procedure was straightforward and simple enough to carry out with minimal oversight.

However, the respondent recommended that the phases of the CCMF be carried out simultaneously with the provision of a procedure or documentation showing guidelines for users.

7.7 Proposed Future Modification for the CCMF

The fifth and sixth questions aim to obtain responses that will help identify areas within the CCMF that need to be enhanced. These areas include the proposal to merge the eligibility and value evaluation phases due to their similar functions. Furthermore, it was also suggested that the aspect of the BSC that had to do with development and learning be moved to phase III. This is because phase III is more directly related to getting employees ready in terms of cloud migration. Further recommendations involve shifting the focus from IT to the business viewpoint, where strategy is ultimately defined. Also, considering business changes which will impact the organisations/businesses using the CCMF for migration decisions. It is necessary to look at the core features of strategy implementation, which include awareness, training and communication across board.

CHAPTER 8 CONCLUSION

8.1 Introduction

This study aids in making business/organisation level Cloud migration choices more straightforward. In order to achieve this, we used the Design Science Research methodology and a case study approach which is adaptive. The research problem associated with this dissertation is the absence of a standardised framework for moving on-premises workloads to the cloud. It is evident from the many Cloud migration processes that there is no universal/comprehensive framework for moving applications to the cloud from on-premises infrastructure.

The dissertation will be wrap-up with this chapter by offering some final thoughts on the research and the evaluation results.

8.2 Dissertation Findings

The purpose of this dissertation was to design a decision framework for migrating to the Cloud to deal with the problems raised. There are four requirements that must be met in order to resolve the research problem.

- *Give detailed criteria for choosing which applications should be moved to the Cloud.*
- *Give explicit justifications and reasons for migration to specified CSPs and Services*
- *Establish precise standards for choosing the best migration strategy depending on the application.*
- *The framework should fit into the needs of small and medium businesses across various industries.*

To further address the highlighted problem, the Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF) is developed within this dissertation for a seamless decision-making process for cloud migration.

The dissertation findings will be discussed, and the findings are shown here. The evaluation results will specify the steps the CCMF took to fix the issues described. Professionals with over ten years of experience within the cloud technology industry were interviewed to evaluate the CCMF's efficacy in a workplace context. Thereafter, information was gathered and evaluated based on their responses. In the subsequent paragraph, we will talk about how the CCMF addresses the issues by conforming to the specified requirements for a successful resolution.

The very first requirement that needs to be talked about is;

The CCMF should have detailed criteria for choosing which applications should be moved to the Cloud

This requirement seeks to determine the eligibility of the application/workload which resides on-premises for cloud migration. This is accomplished by doing an eligibility check, which will be done with an academically accepted tool which measures the workload/applications maintainability, availability and reliability. The tool used to check for eligibility is the RAM paradigm that is widely employed in the field of science research. By reusing an already established tool, we can absolutely guarantee that it will provide accurate results inside the framework. This paradigm examines whether an on-premises application fails to meet an organisation's Service Level Agreement (SLA). If it fails, It is often moved to the cloud, where improved uptime and performance are guaranteed. The eligibility check process can be repeated for every application/workload because the organisation's measures for SLAs have been defined and will not change.

Furthermore, all respondents within this dissertation agree that the eligibility check successfully achieves the goal of a phase that identifies suitable workloads/applications for cloud migration. Some of the respondents also stated that the eligibility check phase could be merged with another phase, but had no dissenting opinion regarding the potential of the check to address issues around the selection of workload/application. Others have recommended expanding the set of measures beyond the RAM paradigm to include interoperability. In light of this, it is safe to say that the requirements for the selection of workloads/applications are met by the eligibility check phase.

The next requirement to be met is:

The CCMF should have explicit justifications and reasons for migration to specified CSPs and Services

To address this requirement, the CCMF was developed to assess how beneficial a cloud migration decision will be to an organisation. In the value evaluation phase, the business plan of an organisation is taken into account to ascertain whether or not there would be a positive impact. The Balanced Scorecard (BSC) is used for strategic analysis of the value of cloud migration to an organisation. The BSC has been extensively studied and published by several researchers, which makes it a reliable and established method for value evaluation.

The viewpoints which the BSC used were centred around the customer, finance, organisational procedures, development and learning. These viewpoints are true reflections of the need for an exceptionally affordable solution. By looking at value propositions from the viewpoints, it is possible to figure out how much value will be added to an organisation if cloud migration is implemented. The justification for value evaluation is making sure that the migration of the workloads/applications to the cloud is of advantage to the organisation.

The respondents who took part in the research evaluation acknowledged that it was important to evaluate the value cloud migration adds to an organisation. Also, one respondent raised concerns about how most organisations may have several areas of interest, which must be taken into account while using the BSC. Further advised that an expert is necessary for proper implementation of BSC. In addition, some of the respondents believed that the viewpoints which the BSC made use of were not enough and that more should be added. The evaluation of the value proposition is performed with the intention of aligning the objectives of the organisation with the migration of workloads/applications.

The third requirement to be met is:

The CCMF should establish precise standards for choosing the best migration strategy depending on the application

Various migration strategies are needed for various applications because of their varying degrees of adaptability to change and complexity. The approach taken while dealing with a complex application will be different as opposed to dealing with a simple one. A precise standard for choosing the best migration strategy makes it easy to choose the most appropriate migration approach for each application/workload. Numerous factors must be considered when selecting the migration approach and service. Whether an application is migrated by rehosting to IaaS, refactoring, refactoring, or repurchasing SaaS depends on how much effort it will take to make it work in the Cloud.

Respondents all acknowledged that the procedure for selecting the cloud migration approach was a realistic solution. Respondents showed an understanding of a variety of research methods while data was being collected and provided valuable feedback on the transition from on-premises to cloud-based infrastructure.

The last requirement is that:

The CCMF should fit into the needs of any organisations across various industries

According to the results of the collected and analysed data, the CCMF is robust and applicable to any workload/application under consideration for cloud migration. The development of the CCMF was done in a manner that makes it flexible enough to be used with any workload, application or cloud service provider. This makes the CCMF a truly comprehensive framework.

The development of the CCMF was successfully used to meet the established requirement within this research. Respondents who participated in the research offered feedback about each requirement outlined. Furthermore, this feedback should be considered in future CCMF modifications. One of the respondents voiced displeasure regarding the way the framework process was initiated and recommended it started with a business point of view rather than the Information technology point of view because decisions within an organisation or business are not driven by Information technology. In section 7.5, we analysed the gathered data and came up with a solution to the defined problem, developing a set of design requirements, creating an artefact that satisfies those requirements, and developing evaluation requirements from the requirement of the solution. Using this method, we were able to keep our attention on the issue at hand as we worked to solve it.

8.3 Contribution of this Dissertation

This dissertation adds to the cloud migration discussion within the research and field professionals community. Addressing its contribution to the group of professionals who work in the field. For an organisation planning to move its workloads/applications from on-premises to the cloud, there will be considerations on the cloud service provider and services to use. Cloud service providers will always offer migration strategies that are tailored to their infrastructure. Due to the reason earlier mentioned, organisations who are evaluating various service providers may find it challenging because of the complexities that emanate from evaluating numerous cloud migration strategies. The CCMF can be used by field professionals to assist organisations in making the right decisions regarding cloud migration. With the help of the CCMF, organisations can easily evaluate the benefit of moving to the cloud and also determine which service provider and application are most appropriate.

Secondly, the dissertation makes a significant addition to the research community. The data supplied by the respondents who took part in the research was a valuable contribution which has helped recognise new research areas. Furthermore, contributions made to the research community were the integration of different frameworks to provide a comprehensive framework for cloud migration decisions. The decisions made within cloud computing can not

be limited to things pertaining to technology alone because the applications that are used within an organisation affect the overall strategy of the organisation.

8.4 Research Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

Several limitations were associated with this dissertation. As a major limitation, this research can only be applied to migrations to the public cloud and does not cut across private, hybrid or community clouds. On-premise workloads/applications migration to the cloud is the primary focus. Another limitation is that this research can not be used to justify the implementation of a new cloud service. The CCMF can still be useful for various kinds of migration despite these limitations. However, additional study is required to ascertain the CCMF's applicability in different Cloud migration contexts.

The respondent who participated in this research offered a wide variety of recommendations for improving the framework. Some recommendations for Phase I are to broaden the scope beyond maintenance, availability and reliability to incorporate additional evaluative measures. Also, the suggestion to merge Phases I and II into a single evaluative phase. To improve the BSC in Phase II, it is suggested that more viewpoints be included to complement the predefined ones. The added views are associated with risk assessment and regulatory obligations. Lastly, it is advised to develop a document and a process diagram or flow chart to direct individuals to implement the artefact properly. The recommendations made by respondents have provided improvements that could be made to the CCMF to make it further comprehensive and accessible.

References

- Abah, J. and Ogwueleka, F. (2013) 'Cloud Computing with Related Enabling Technologies', *International Journal of Cloud Computing and Services Science (IJ-CLOSER)*, 1, pp. 258–267. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11591/closer.v2i1.1720>.
- Abdulkader, S.J. and Abualkishik, A.M. (2013) 'Cloud computing and e-commerce in small and medium enterprises (sme's): the benefits, challenges', *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 2(12), pp. 285–288.
- Adebisi, A.A., Adekanmi, A.A. and Oluwatobi, A.E. (2014) 'A study of cloud computing in the university enterprise', *International Journal of Advanced Computer Research*, 4(2), p. 450.
- Ahmad, N., Naveed, Q.N. and Hoda, N. (2018) 'Strategy and procedures for Migration to the Cloud Computing', in 2018 IEEE 5th International Conference on Engineering Technologies and Applied Sciences (ICETAS). 2018 IEEE 5th International Conference on Engineering Technologies and Applied Sciences (ICETAS), pp. 1–5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICETAS.2018.8629101>.
- Aken, J.E. van (2004) 'Management Research Based on the Paradigm of the Design Sciences: The Quest for Field-Tested and Grounded Technological Rules', *Journal of Management Studies*, 41(2), pp. 219–246. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2004.00430.x>.
- Alharbi, F., Atkins, A. and Stanier, C. (2017a) 'Cloud Computing Adoption in Healthcare Organisations: A Qualitative Study in Saudi Arabia', in A. Hameurlain et al. (eds) *Transactions on Large-Scale Data- and Knowledge-Centered Systems XXXV*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), pp. 96–131. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-56121-8_5.
- Alharbi, F., Atkins, A. and Stanier, C. (2017b) 'Cloud computing adoption readiness assessment in saudi healthcare organisations: a strategic view', in *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Internet of things, Data and Cloud Computing*. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery (ICC '17), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3018896.3025156>.
- Alkhalil, A., Sahandi, R. and John, D. (2016) 'A Decision Process Model to Support Migration to Cloud Computing', *International Journal of Business Information Systems*, 24(1), pp. 102–126.

Alosaimi, R. and Alnuem, M. (2016) 'Risk management frameworks for cloud computing: a critical review', *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology*, 8(4), p. 1.

Alouffi, B. et al. (2021) 'A Systematic Literature Review on Cloud Computing Security: Threats and Mitigation Strategies', *IEEE Access*, 9, pp. 57792–57807. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3073203>.

Amazon (2022) Amazon S3 Simple Storage Service Pricing - Amazon Web Services, Amazon Web Services, Inc. Available at: <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/pricing/> (Accessed: 4 September 2022).

Andriy, S. (2021) Top Cloud Service Providers: A Quick Comparison - Avenga. Available at: <https://www.avenga.com/magazine/top-cloud-service-providers/> (Accessed: 11 August 2022).

Armbrust, M. et al. (2009) Above the clouds: A berkeley view of cloud computing. Technical Report UCB/EECS-2009-28, EECS Department, University of California

Armbrust, M. et al. (2010) 'A view of cloud computing', *Communications of the ACM*, 53(4), pp. 50–58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1721654.1721672>.

AWS (2017) Summary of the Amazon S3 Service Disruption in the Northern Virginia (US-EAST-1) Region, Amazon Web Services, Inc. Available at: <https://aws.amazon.com/message/41926/> (Accessed: 15 July 2022).

AWS (2022) Secure and resizable cloud compute – Amazon EC2 – Amazon Web Services, Amazon Web Services, Inc. Available at: <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/> (Accessed: 11 July 2022).

AWS Prescriptive Guidance (2022) Amazon Web Services, Inc. Available at: <https://aws.amazon.com/prescriptive-guidance/> (Accessed: 8 July 2022).

Aydin, N. (2015) 'Cloud computing for E-commerce', *IOSR Journal of Mobile Computing & Application*, 2(1), pp. 27–31.

Azure (2022) Azure Storage Blobs Pricing | Microsoft Azure. Available at: <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-gb/pricing/details/storage/blobs/> (Accessed: 4 September 2022).

Baiardi, F. and Sgandurra, D. (2010) 'Securing a Community Cloud', in 2010 IEEE 30th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems Workshops. 2010 IEEE 30th

International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems Workshops, pp. 32–41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCSW.2010.34>.

Baskerville, R. et al. (2016) ‘Bounded creativity in design science research’.

Beck, A., Reck, J. and Siegfried, P. (2022) ‘Development of a Performance Measurement Systems for NCA-Sales-Teams’, *Oblik i finansi*, 95, pp. 65–87.

Beserra, P.V. et al. (2012) ‘Cloudstep: A step-by-step decision process to support legacy application migration to the cloud’, in 2012 IEEE 6th International Workshop on the Maintenance and Evolution of Service-Oriented and Cloud-Based Systems (MESOCA). 2012 IEEE 6th International Workshop on the Maintenance and Evolution of Service-Oriented and Cloud-Based Systems (MESOCA), pp. 7–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MESOCA.2012.6392602>.

Binz, T. et al. (2014) ‘Migration of enterprise applications to the cloud’, *it - Information Technology*, 56(3), pp. 106–111. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/itit-2013-1032>.

Canalys (2022) Canalys Newsroom - Global cloud infrastructure market Q4 2020. Available at: <https://www.canalys.com/newsroom/global-cloud-market-q4-2020> (Accessed: 11 August 2022).

Carroll, M., Van Der Merwe, A. and Kotze, P. (2011) ‘Secure cloud computing: Benefits, risks and controls’, in 2011 Information Security for South Africa. IEEE, pp. 1–9.

Cerveira, F., Barbosa, R. and Madeira, H. (2021) ‘Mitigating Virtualization Failures Through Migration to a Co-Located Hypervisor’, *IEEE Access*, 9, pp. 105255–105269. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3098644>.

Chen, J. (2020) ‘Azure Fundamental: IaaS, PaaS, SaaS’, *The Programmer In Kiwiland*. Available at: <https://medium.com/chenjd-xyz/azure-fundamental-iaas-paas-saas-973e0c406de7> (Accessed: 12 July 2022).

Chou, D.C. (2015) ‘Cloud computing: A value creation model’, *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, 38, pp. 72–77. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csi.2014.10.001>.

Cisco (2022) What Is Cloud Migration Strategy? The Process, Plans, and Costs, Cisco. Available at: https://www.cisco.com/c/en_uk/solutions/cloud/what-is-a-cloud-migration-strategy.html (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

Cleven, A., Gubler, P. and Hüner, K.M. (2009) 'Design alternatives for the evaluation of design science research artifacts', in Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Design Science Research in Information Systems and Technology. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery (DESRIST '09), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1555619.1555645>.

Crotty, M. (2020) The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003115700>.

CSCC (2022) Cloud Council, Cloud Council. Available at: <https://www.cloud-council.org/> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

Dhai, A. and McQuoid-Mason, D.J. (2010) Bioethics, human rights and health law: Principles and practice. Juta and Company Ltd.

Dhaya, R., Kanthavel, R. and Venusamy, K. (2021) 'Dynamic secure and automated infrastructure for private cloud data center', Annals of Operations Research [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-021-04442-0>.

Dillon, T., Wu, C. and Chang, E. (2010) 'Cloud Computing: Issues and Challenges', in 2010 24th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications. 2010 24th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications, pp. 27–33. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/AINA.2010.187>.

DMTF (2022) Standards and Technology | DMTF. Available at: <https://www.dmtf.org/standards> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

Ellison, M., Calinescu, R. and Paige, R.F. (2018) 'Evaluating cloud database migration options using workload models', Journal of Cloud Computing, 7(1), p. 6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13677-018-0108-5>.

ETSI (2022) ETSI ICT Standards for free, ETSI. Available at: <https://www.etsi.org/standards> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

Fernández, A. et al. (2012) 'An Overview of E-Learning in Cloud Computing', in L. Uden et al. (eds) Workshop on Learning Technology for Education in Cloud (LTEC'12). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer (Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing), pp. 35–46. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-30859-8_4.

Ferrer, A.J. et al. (2012) 'OPTIMIS: A holistic approach to cloud service provisioning', *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 28(1), pp. 66–77. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2011.05.022>.

Feuerlicht, G., Burkon, L. and Sebesta, M. (2011) 'Cloud computing adoption: What are the issues', *System Integration*, 18(2), pp. 187–192.

Foster, I. et al. (2009) 'Cloud Computing and Grid Computing 360-Degree Compared', *Cloud Computing and Grid Computing 360-Degree Compared*, 5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/GCE.2008.4738445>.

Garg, S.K., Versteeg, S. and Buyya, R. (2011) 'SMICloud: A Framework for Comparing and Ranking Cloud Services', in 2011 Fourth IEEE International Conference on Utility and Cloud Computing. 2011 Fourth IEEE International Conference on Utility and Cloud Computing, pp. 210–218. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/UCC.2011.36>.

Gartner (2021) Gartner Reprint. Available at: <https://www.gartner.com/doc/reprints?id=1-2710E4VR&ct=210802&st=sb> (Accessed: 11 August 2022).

Ghahramani, M.H., Zhou, M. and Hon, C.T. (2017) 'Toward cloud computing QoS architecture: analysis of cloud systems and cloud services', *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, 4(1), pp. 6–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JAS.2017.7510313>.

Google Cloud (2022a) Adoption Framework, Google Cloud. Available at: <https://cloud.google.com/adoption-framework> (Accessed: 11 August 2022).

Google Cloud (2022b) Pricing | Cloud Storage | Google Cloud. Available at: <https://cloud.google.com/storage/pricing> (Accessed: 4 September 2022).

Goyal, S. (2014) 'Public vs private vs hybrid vs community-cloud computing: a critical review', *International Journal of Computer Network and Information Security*, 6(3), pp. 20–29.

Hancock, D.R., Algozzine, B. and Lim, J.H. (2021) 'Doing case study research: A practical guide for beginning researchers'.

Hashemi, S.M. and Bardsiri, A.K. (2012) 'Cloud computing vs. grid computing', *ARNP journal of systems and software*, 2(5), pp. 188–194.

Herbst, N.R., Kounev, S. and Reussner, R. (2013) 'Elasticity in Cloud Computing: What It Is, and What It Is Not', in. 10th International Conference on Autonomic Computing (ICAC 13),

pp. 23–27. Available at: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/icac13/technical-sessions/presentation/herbst> (Accessed: 13 July 2022).

Hevner, A.R. and Wickramasinghe, N. (2018) ‘Design Science Research Opportunities in Health Care’, in N. Wickramasinghe and J.L. Schaffer (eds) *Theories to Inform Superior Health Informatics Research and Practice*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Healthcare Delivery in the Information Age), pp. 3–18. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72287-0_1.

Horváth, I. (2007) ‘Comparison of three methodological approaches of design research’, in *DS 42: Proceedings of ICED 2007, the 16th International Conference on Engineering Design*, Paris, France, 28.-31.07. 2007, pp. 361–362.

Hu, Z. et al. (2014) ‘The Need for End-to-End Evaluation of Cloud Availability’, in M. Faloutsos and A. Kuzmanovic (eds) *Passive and Active Measurement*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), pp. 119–130. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-04918-2_12.

Hugos, M.H. and Hulitzky, D. (2010) *Business in the Cloud: What Every Business Needs to Know About Cloud Computing*. John Wiley & Sons.

IBM (2022) *Cloud Consulting and Migration Services | IBM, Cloud Consulting and Migration Services | IBM*. Available at: <https://www.ibm.com/services/cloud/migration> (Accessed: 8 July 2022).

Iivari, J. and Venable, J. (2009) ‘Action research and design science research - Seemingly similar but decisively dissimilar’, *ECIS 2009 Proceedings [Preprint]*. Available at: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/ecis2009/73>.

ISO (2022) *ISO - Standards*, ISO. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/standards.html> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

Jadeja, Y. and Modi, K. (2012) ‘Cloud computing - concepts, architecture and challenges’, in *2012 International Conference on Computing, Electronics and Electrical Technologies (ICCEET)*. 2012 International Conference on Computing, Electronics and Electrical Technologies (ICCEET), pp. 877–880. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCEET.2012.6203873>.

Jamsa, K. (2012) *Cloud Computing: SaaS, PaaS, IaaS, Virtualization, Business Models, Mobile, Security and More*. Jones & Bartlett Publishers.

- Jamshidi, P. et al. (2015) 'Cloud Migration Patterns: A Multi-cloud Service Architecture Perspective', in F. Toumani et al. (eds) *Service-Oriented Computing - ICSOC 2014 Workshops*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), pp. 6–19. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-22885-3_2.
- Jarvinen, P. (2007) 'On reviewing of results in design research'.
- Kaur, R. kamal, Pandey, B. and Singh, L.K. (2018) 'Dependability analysis of safety critical systems: Issues and challenges', *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 120, pp. 127–154. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2018.05.027>.
- Kavis, M.J. (2014) *Architecting the Cloud: Design Decisions for Cloud Computing Service Models (SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS)*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kumalo, N.H. and van der Poll, J.A. (2018) 'The role of cloud computing in addressing small, medium enterprise challenges in South Africa', Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. University of South Africa, South Africa [Preprint].
- Kumar, M. and Sharma, S.C. (2018) 'Deadline constrained based dynamic load balancing algorithm with elasticity in cloud environment', *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 69, pp. 395–411. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2017.11.018>.
- Kundra, V. (2011) 'Federal cloud computing strategy'.
- Kuo, M.-H. (2011) 'Opportunities and Challenges of Cloud Computing to Improve Health Care Services', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 13(3), p. e1867. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.1867>.
- Lampe, U. et al. (2012) 'Cloud Computing in the Financial Industry – A Road Paved with Security Pitfalls?', *AMCIS 2012 Proceedings* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/amcis2012/proceedings/ISSecurity/4>.
- Li, B. et al. (2014) 'Research and Applications of Cloud Manufacturing in China', *Cloud-Based Design and Manufacturing (CBDM): A Service-Oriented Product Development Paradigm for the 21st Century*, pp. 89–126. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-07398-9_4.
- Liu, S. et al. (2018) 'Understanding the effect of cloud computing on organisational agility: An empirical examination', *International Journal of Information Management*, 43, pp. 98–111. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.07.010>.

- Loebbecke, C., Thomas, B. and Ullrich, T. (2011) ‘Assessing Cloud Readiness: Introducing the Magic Matrices Method Used by Continental AG’, in M. Nüttgens et al. (eds) *Governance and Sustainability in Information Systems. Managing the Transfer and Diffusion of IT*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer (IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology), pp. 270–281. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-24148-2_18.
- Marston, S. et al. (2011) ‘Cloud computing — The business perspective’, *Decision Support Systems*, 51(1), pp. 176–189. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2010.12.006>.
- Mdletshe, S., Oliveira, M. and Twala, B. (2021) ‘Enhancing medical radiation science education through a design science research methodology’, *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences*, 52(2), pp. 172–178. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmir.2021.01.005>.
- Mell, P. and Grance, T. (2011) ‘The NIST definition of cloud computing’.
- Melnikovas, A. (2018) ‘Towards an explicit research methodology: Adapting research onion model for futures studies’, *Journal of Futures Studies*, 23(2), pp. 29–44.
- Microsoft (2021) Microsoft Services Agreement. Available at: <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/servicesagreement> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).
- Microsoft (2022a) Microsoft Cloud Adoption Framework for Azure - Cloud Adoption Framework. Available at: <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/cloud-adoption-framework/> (Accessed: 8 July 2022).
- Microsoft (2022b) Virtual Machines (VMs) for Linux and Windows | Microsoft Azure. Available at: <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/virtual-machines/> (Accessed: 11 July 2022).
- Mikalef, P. and Pateli, A. (2017) ‘Information technology-enabled dynamic capabilities and their indirect effect on competitive performance: Findings from PLS-SEM and fsQCA’, *Journal of Business Research*, 70, pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.09.004>.
- Miyachi, C. (2018) ‘What is “Cloud”? It is time to update the NIST definition?’, *IEEE Cloud computing*, 5(03), pp. 6–11.
- Mohammed, B. and Kiran, M. (2014) ‘Experimental Report on Setting up a Cloud Computing Environment at the University of Bradford’.

Mungwini, M. (2018) Business strategies of organisations in a challenging economy: the case of mobile company X Zimbabwe (MCXZ). PhD Thesis.

Mushi, T.N. (2020) The design, development and evaluation of a holistic cloud migration decision framework. PhD Thesis.

Nayar, K.B. and Kumar, V. (2018) 'Cost benefit analysis of cloud computing in education', *International Journal of Business Information Systems*, 27(2), pp. 205–221.

Nazir, A. and Jamshed, S. (2013) Cloud Computing: Challenges and Concerns for its Adoption in Indian SMEs. *International Journal of Software and Web Sciences*, 4(2), pp. 120-125. - Google Search. Available at: [https://www.google.com/search?q=Nazir%2C+A.+%26+Jamshed%2C+S.%2C+2013.+Cloud+Computing%3A+Challenges+and+Concerns+for+its+Adoption+in+Indian+SMEs.+International+Journal+of+Software+and+Web+Sciences%2C+4\(2\)%2C+pp.+120-125.&rlz=1C1CHBF_en-GBGB1004GB1004&oq=Nazir%2C+A.+%26+Jamshed%2C+S.%2C+2013.+Cloud+Computing%3A+Challenges+and+Concerns+for+its+Adoption+in+Indian+SMEs.+International+Journal+of+Software+and+Web+Sciences%2C+4\(2\)%2C+pp.+120-125.&aqs=chrome..69i57j69i60.1182j0j15&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8](https://www.google.com/search?q=Nazir%2C+A.+%26+Jamshed%2C+S.%2C+2013.+Cloud+Computing%3A+Challenges+and+Concerns+for+its+Adoption+in+Indian+SMEs.+International+Journal+of+Software+and+Web+Sciences%2C+4(2)%2C+pp.+120-125.&rlz=1C1CHBF_en-GBGB1004GB1004&oq=Nazir%2C+A.+%26+Jamshed%2C+S.%2C+2013.+Cloud+Computing%3A+Challenges+and+Concerns+for+its+Adoption+in+Indian+SMEs.+International+Journal+of+Software+and+Web+Sciences%2C+4(2)%2C+pp.+120-125.&aqs=chrome..69i57j69i60.1182j0j15&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8) (Accessed: 15 July 2022).

Nedbal, D. et al. (2014) 'The Adoption of Cloud Services in the Context of Organisations: An examination of drivers and barriers'.

NIST (2016) Cloud Computing | CSRC | CSRC, CSRC | NIST. Available at: <https://csrc.nist.gov/projects/cloud-computing> (Accessed: 11 July 2022).

NIST (2022) National Institute of Standards and Technology, NIST. Available at: <https://www.nist.gov/> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

OASIS (2022) Standards Archive, OASIS Open. Available at: <https://www.oasis-open.org/standards/> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

Oke, A.E. et al. (2021) 'Exploring the benefits of cloud computing for sustainable construction in Nigeria', *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-04-2021-0189>.

Omollo, Z.O. (2015) The Balanced Scorecard as a Strategy Implementation and Performance Measurement Tool at the Parliamentary Service Commission of Kenya. Thesis. University of

Nairobi. Available at: <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/94949> (Accessed: 11 September 2022).

Orange Business Services (2019) Cloud: the new business continuity challenge | Orange Business Services. Available at: <http://www.orange-business.com/en/library/white-paper/cloud-new-business-continuity-challenge> (Accessed: 15 July 2022).

Panori, A. et al. (2016) 'Migration of applications to the Cloud: a user-driven approach', *Journal of Smart Cities (Transferred)*, 2(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.18063/JSC.2016.01.005>.

Peffer, K. et al. (2020) 'Design Science Research Process: A Model for Producing and Presenting Information Systems Research'. arXiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2006.02763>.

Priya, P. (2019) 'Cloud Computing Technologies | Know Best Technologies With Benefits', EDUCBA, 6 October. Available at: <https://www.educba.com/cloud-computing-technologies/> (Accessed: 13 July 2022).

Priyambiga, M.R. and Patil, S. (2021) 'A review on Cloud Computing and Cloud Service Providers'.

Rahko, D. (2016) The Realities of XaaS (Everything-as-a-Service), BitTitan. Available at: <https://www.bittitan.com/blog/realities-everything-service-xaas/> (Accessed: 11 July 2022).

RedHat (2022a) Product Documentation for Red Hat Application Migration Toolkit 4.3, Red Hat Customer Portal. Available at: https://access.redhat.com/documentation/en-us/red_hat_application_migration_toolkit/4.3 (Accessed: 8 July 2022).

RedHat (2022b) What are cloud services? Available at: <https://www.redhat.com/en/topics/cloud-computing/what-are-cloud-services> (Accessed: 11 July 2022).

Reubens, R. (2016) To craft, by design, for sustainability: Towards holistic sustainability design for developing-country enterprises. Dissertation (TU Delft). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4233/uuid:0c2c14c8-9550-449d-b1ff-7e0588ccd6c2>.

Rimal, B.P. et al. (2011) 'Architectural requirements for cloud computing systems: an enterprise cloud approach', *Journal of Grid Computing*, 9(1), pp. 3–26.

Robison, S. (2008) 'The next wave: Everything as a service', *Executive Viewpoint*: [www. hp.com](http://www.hp.com), p. 39.

Saini, H., Upadhyaya, A. and Khandelwal, M.K. (2019) 'Benefits of Cloud Computing for Business Enterprises: A Review'. Rochester, NY. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3463631>.

Satzger, B. et al. (2013) 'Winds of Change: From Vendor Lock-In to the Meta Cloud', *IEEE Internet Computing*, 17(1), pp. 69–73. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2013.19>.

Schneider, S. and Sunyaev, A. (2016) 'Determinant factors of cloud-sourcing decisions: reflecting on the IT outsourcing literature in the era of cloud computing', *Journal of Information Technology*, 31(1), pp. 1–31.

Shoniwa, T.R. (2016) 'Exploring the adoption of cloud computing as a business : a Bulawayo Small to Medium Enterprises (SMSs) Study'. Available at: <https://uir.unisa.ac.za/handle/10500/22194> (Accessed: 12 July 2022).

Sitaram, D. and Manjunath, G. (2011) *Moving To The Cloud: Developing Apps in the New World of Cloud Computing*. Elsevier.

Sonnenberg, C. and vom Brocke, J. (2012) 'Evaluations in the Science of the Artificial – Reconsidering the Build-Evaluate Pattern in Design Science Research', in K. Peffers, M. Rothenberger, and B. Kuechler (eds) *Design Science Research in Information Systems. Advances in Theory and Practice*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), pp. 381–397. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-29863-9_28.

Staffordshire University Libraries, A.S. (2022) *Library: Finding resources: Searching and support*. Available at: <https://libguides.staffs.ac.uk/c.php?g=681978&p=4864632> (Accessed: 10 July 2022).

Stephen, O. (2016) *6 Strategies for Migrating Applications to the Cloud | AWS Cloud Enterprise Strategy Blog*. Available at: <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/enterprise-strategy/6-strategies-for-migrating-applications-to-the-cloud/> (Accessed: 29 August 2022).

Strauch, S. et al. (2012) 'Cloud Data Patterns for Confidentiality.', *CLOSER*, 12, pp. 387–394.

Sultan, N. (2010) 'Cloud computing for education: A new dawn?', *International Journal of Information Management*, 30(2), pp. 109–116. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2009.09.004>.

Tak, B.C., Uргаonkar, B. and Sivasubramaniam, A. (2011) 'To move or not to move: The economics of cloud computing', in *3rd USENIX Workshop on Hot Topics in Cloud Computing (HotCloud 11)*.

Taleb, T., Ksentini, A. and Jantti, R. (2016) “‘Anything as a Service’ for 5G Mobile Systems’, IEEE Network, 30(6), pp. 84–91. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.2016.1500244RP>.

Vaishnavi, V. and Kuechler, W. (2004) ‘Design research in information systems’.

Varia, J. (2010) ‘Migrating your existing applications to the aws cloud’, A Phase-driven Approach to Cloud Migration, pp. 1–23.

Venable, J., Pries-Heje, J. and Baskerville, R. (2012) ‘A Comprehensive Framework for Evaluation in Design Science Research’, in K. Peffers, M. Rothenberger, and B. Kuechler (eds) Design Science Research in Information Systems. Advances in Theory and Practice. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), pp. 423–438. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-29863-9_31.

Vignos, J., Kim, P. and Metzger, R.L. (2013) ‘Demystifying the fog: Cloud computing from a risk management perspective’, Special Issue: Cloud Computing [Preprint].

Vinoth, S. et al. (2022) ‘Application of cloud computing in banking and e-commerce and related security threats’, Materials Today: Proceedings, 51, pp. 2172–2175. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.11.121>.

VMware (2022a) Virtualization Technology & Virtual Machine Software: What is Virtualization?, VMware. Available at: <https://www.vmware.com/solutions/virtualization.html> (Accessed: 13 July 2022).

VMware (2022b) What is a Cloud Migration Strategy? | VMware Glossary, VMware. Available at: <https://www.vmware.com/topics/glossary/content/cloud-migration-strategy.html> (Accessed: 17 July 2022).

Weber, S. (2012) ‘Comparing Key Characteristics Of Design Science Research As An Approach And Paradigm’, PACIS 2012 Proceedings [Preprint]. Available at: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/pacis2012/180>.

Weinman, J. (2016) ‘Hybrid Cloud Economics’, IEEE Cloud Computing, 3(1), pp. 18–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCC.2016.27>.

Whaiduzzaman, M. et al. (2014) ‘Cloud service selection using multicriteria decision analysis’, The Scientific World Journal, 2014.

Xue, C.T.S. and Xin, F.T.W. (2016) 'Benefits and challenges of the adoption of cloud computing in business', *International Journal on Cloud Computing: Services and Architecture*, 6(6), pp. 01–15.

Yeboah-Boateng, E.O. and Essandoh, K.A. (2014) 'Factors influencing the adoption of cloud computing by small and medium enterprises in developing economies', *International Journal of Emerging Science and Engineering*, 2(4), pp. 13–20.

Young, D.A. (2015) 'Improving the adoption of cloud computing by small & medium scale enterprise (SMEs) in Nigeria'. Available at: <https://uir.unisa.ac.za/handle/10500/19212> (Accessed: 14 July 2022).

Yumpu.com (2011) Concepts, Challenges and Opportunities of Cloud Computing for ..., yumpu.com. Available at: <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/read/33336695/concepts-challenges-and-opportunities-of-cloud-computing-for-> (Accessed: 14 July 2022).

Zhao, J.-F. and Zhou, J.-T. (2014) 'Strategies and methods for cloud migration', *international Journal of Automation and Computing*, 11(2), pp. 143–152.

Annexe A: Proportionate Ethics Form

RESEARCH ETHICS

Proportionate Review Form

The Proportionate Review process may be used where the proposed research raises only minimal ethical risk. This research must: focus on minimally sensitive topics; entail minimal intrusion or disruption to others; and involve participants who would not be considered vulnerable in the context of the research.

PART A: TO BE COMPLETED BY RESEARCHER

Name of Researcher:	OLUWATOBI FADOKUN		
School	SCHOOL OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AND ARTS		
Student/Course Details (If Applicable)			
Student ID Number:	21025184		
Name of Supervisor(s)/Module Tutor:	LUTTA PANTALEON ODONGO		
PhD/MPhil project:	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Taught Postgraduate Project/Assignment:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Award Title:	MSC COMPUTER NETWORKS AND SECURITY
Undergraduate Project/Assignment:	<input type="checkbox"/>	Module Title:	DISSERTATION - COIS71052
Project Title:	A Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework: The Development, Implementation and Evaluation		
Project Outline:	This dissertation aims to develop a consistent approach/framework to cloud migration initiatives. A Comprehensive Cloud Migration Framework (CCMF) has developed within this dissertation for seamless cloud migration. The Design Science Research (DSR) was the qualitative research approach utilised. This research approach was used because the actual outcome of the research is a problem-solving innovation. The CCMF was structured, implemented and evaluated using the DSR approach with an adaptive test case. Based on the reviewed literature, the CCMF is an effective solution for cloud migration challenges. It can be used on any project involving cloud migration. Improvement opportunities will be looked out for throughout the research, which will be considered in subsequent studies..		
Give a brief description of participants and procedure (methods, tests etc.)	Interview with respondents		
Expected Start Date:	01/02/2022	Expected End Date:	27/05/2022

Relevant professional body ethical guidelines should be consulted when completing this form.

Please seek guidance from the School Ethics Coordinator if you are uncertain about any ethical issues arising from this application.

There is an obligation on the researcher and supervisor (where applicable) to bring to the attention of the School Ethics Coordinator any issues with ethical implications not identified by this form.

Researcher Declaration

I consider that this project has no significant ethical implications requiring full ethical review		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
I confirm that:		
1.	The research will NOT involve members of vulnerable groups. Vulnerable groups include but are not limited to: children and young people (under 18 years of age), those with a learning disability or cognitive impairment, patients, people in custody, people engaged in illegal activities (e.g. drug taking), or individuals in a dependent or unequal relationship.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2.	The research will NOT involve sensitive topics. Sensitive topics include, but are not limited to: participants' sexual behaviour, their illegal or political behaviour, their experience of violence, their abuse or exploitation, their mental health, their gender or ethnic status. The research must not involve groups where permission of a gatekeeper is normally required for initial access to members, for example, ethnic or cultural groups, native peoples or indigenous communities.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3.	The research will NOT deliberately mislead participants in any way.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4.	The research will NOT involve access to records of personal or confidential information, including genetic or other biological information, concerning identifiable individuals.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5.	The research will NOT induce psychological stress, anxiety or humiliation, cause more than minimal pain, or involve intrusive interventions. This includes, but is not limited to: the administration of drugs or other substances, vigorous physical exercise, or techniques such as hypnotherapy which may cause participants to reveal information which could cause concern, in the course of their everyday life.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6.	<p>The research WILL be conducted with participants' full and informed consent at the time the study is carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main procedure will be explained to participants in advance, so that they are informed about what to expect. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> • Participants will be told their involvement in the research is voluntary. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> • Written consent will be obtained from participants. (<i>This is not required for self-completion questionnaires as submission of the completed questionnaire implies consent to participate</i>). <input type="checkbox"/> • Participants will be informed about how they may withdraw from the research at any time and for any reason. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> • For questionnaires and interviews: Participants will be given the option of omitting questions they do not want to answer. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> • Participants will be told that their data will be treated with full confidentiality and that, if published, every effort will be made to ensure it will not be identifiable as theirs. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> • Participants will be given the opportunity to be debriefed i.e. to find out more about the study and its results. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 	<p>YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>N/A <input type="checkbox"/></p>
7.	A risk assessment has been completed for this research project	YES

		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/>
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If you are unable to confirm any of the above statements, please complete a Full Ethical Review Form. If the research will include participants that are patients, please complete the Independent Peer Review process.

8. Information and Data Please provide answers to the following questions regarding the handling and storage of information and data:
a) How will research data be stored (manually or electronically)? Electronically
b) How is protection given to the participants (e.g. by being made anonymous through coding and with a participant identifier code being kept separately and securely)? By being anonymous, and responses securely kept.
c) What assurance will be given to the participant about the confidentiality of this data and the security of its storage? It will be stored in a safe hard drive.
d) Is assurance given to the participant that they cannot be identified from any publication or dissemination of the results of the project? Yes, assurance is given, and the questionnaire is anonymously filled.
e) Who will have access to this data, and for what purposes? Nobody, except myself
f) How will the data be stored, for how long, and how will it be discarded? Stored in a secured drive, and destroyed after the dissertation.

Supporting Documentation

All key documents e.g. consent form, information sheet, questionnaire/interview schedule are appended to this application.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
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Signature of Researcher:	OLUWATOBI FADOKUN	Date:	21/06/2022
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NB: If the research departs from the protocol which provides the basis for this proportionate review, then further review will be required and the applicant and supervisor(s) should consider whether or not the proportionate review remains appropriate. If it is no longer appropriate a full ethical review form **MUST** be submitted for consideration by the School Ethics Coordinator .

Annexe B: Risk Assessment Form

RISK ASSESSMENT FORM - MSc Computing Dissertation

When completing this form, the supervision team should try to stay within the more detailed guidance contained in the University's Health & Safety Policy, available at: http://www.staffs.ac.uk/assets/Risk%20Assessment%20Policy_tcm44-14297.pdf
The Policy is more detailed than the MSc risk assessment needs to be, but it covers the responsibilities of academic staff in student projects. Supervisors should note that this responsibility cannot be discharged by relying upon the student's perceived competence. Supervision teams will find, in addition to information on laboratory and studio-based risks this Policy contains health and safety guidance likely to be of relevant to most topic areas.

The supervisor and student should place areas of work into the following risk categories:

- A** = Those where work may not be undertaken without direct supervision;
- B** = Those where work may not be started without the supervisor's advice and approval;
- C** = Activities which can only be undertaken unsupervised after appropriate training.
- D** = Those with risks (other than categories A & B) where extra care must be observed, but where it is considered that this student is already adequately trained and competent in the procedures involved;
- E** = Those where the risks are insignificant and carry no special supervision

Nature and Method of Work	Hazards/Risks	Safeguards/ Training Requirements	Category (A-E)
Research and Analysis of received Questionnaires and interview responses	None	None	E

Considerations.

An example of each risk, how it might arise and the safeguards and category is given below.

Nature and Method of Work	Hazards/Risks	Safeguards	Category (A-E)
Attempt to harness lightning to power a server	Death by electrocution	Use of Faraday cage and rubber boots	A
Site visit to factory to carry out survey or observe processes	Injury through falling tripping or industrial accident #	Observing subject company's health and safety guidelines, wearing protective equipment	

Signatures:

Student:OLUWATOBI FADOKUN..... Date: ... 21/06/2022.....

Supervisor:PANTALEON LUTTA..... Date:24/06/2022.....

Annexe C: Respondents' Responses to Interview Question

Question 1:

- a) Is the CCMF considered a comprehensive model for making cloud migration decisions?
- b) Will the CCMF be applicable to every Cloud migration decision?

Respondent A:

I will say a yes and quite elaborate. Looking at the CCMF holistically, I find some grey areas, probably because of my expertise. These areas have to do with the interoperability of existing systems with the proposed system. From your phase II, which talks about the consideration of maintenance, availability and reliability within the eligibility check, this does not seem to consider the area I just raised. I believe interoperability should also be one of the things to consider.

Respondent B:

I feel the CCMF is covering quite a broad perspective. My opinion is a little different about you beginning with eligibility evaluation. Suppose this is solely approached from the standpoint of a business like "Company A". In that case, I think an evaluation of the value associated should come first. The popular and common assumption when comparing business and information technology is how business is driven by information technology. As an illustration, if we are to create a strategy for a business, the first thing will be the development of a business plan. Next comes the information technology strategy formed from the initially developed plan. So making sure that the business and information technology aspect matches are vital for continuity. The concern I have is that the eligibility criteria phase, which is based on maintenance, availability and reliability measure, are almost entirely focused on technological issues. Looking deeply, you should have a clearer picture of my perspective.

Respondent C:

The advent of cloud technology initiated a new way and approach to IT. Has a cloud architect who is mostly part of the initial process of developing a solution within the cloud and is also a keen advocate of capabilities within the cloud environment. I will say the CCMF eligibility criteria phase, which is based on maintenance, availability and reliability, is great for me. Most notably is the reliability criteria that determine how efficiently a system functions. This shows that the CCMF will also consider migration decisions from the

perspective of making sure that a solution performs as required, making it dependable. I will generally consider the CCMF a comprehensive solution due to its comprehensive approach to cloud migration decisions.

Regarding the applicability of CCMF to every cloud migration decision, I am happy that the BSC was the chosen framework in phase II because it addresses the management of performance from a broad perspective, including adopting a solution. Also, regarding the evaluation of cloud readiness covered in phase III, it was a great idea to look into that aspect. I believe company A is well positioned for cloud migration. Two things which I also believe should be looked into are the network capacity and the ability of the organisation to withstand the changes to be made. It is crucial to consider how we will get there. An example is two key aspects we are looking at regarding the evaluation of office 365. Firstly is how we are going to move over, which the evaluation takes care of, and secondly is the question of how dependable is the cloud service. No one wants to take up something well-known that does not accomplish its objective.

Respondent D:

It is a great body of work, and I must say you have been able to give a structure to the CCMF clearly. However, one question I believe needs clarification is where the Total Cost of Ownership will be placed. Looking at the second phase where you used the BSC to do value evaluation, how much of the initial expenditures before deployment have been captured? Giving consideration to a holistic value being the total cost of ownership and not just the cost of migrating to the cloud, will be a more realistic value evaluation.

Question 2:

- a) When making decisions, does the CCMF consider anything else besides from cost?
- b) What additional aspects must be considered before making decisions while using CCMF?

Respondent A:

I believe the CCMF has shown consideration for other areas aside from cost. And regarding cost, I believe even with the cost, it was quite extensive, considering the cost associated with infrastructure and data. Regarding additional aspects to consider, I made mentioned interoperability been one of the necessary checks to be made within the framework.

Respondent B:

Looking at what you have so far, it is actually detailed. The only thing which comes to my mind is considering the perspective of governance and probably more about managing risk. Also, the value assessment phase should be given a more in-depth approach than just the BSC. As indicated earlier, the area of governance might be worth keeping precisely as a point of reference. With respect to cost or anything additional from the finance perspective, I will advise also that you seek directions from professionals who can present a justifiable framework to capture all expenditures totally.

Respondent C:

What I will like to add looks abstract, but in all sincerity, having the right set of mind for cloud migration and proper assessment is key, but having the right people on board is even more critical. The framework needs to look from the angle of not just IT organisations but also deeply into businesses intending to make use of cloud services. Maybe a general community where everyone could have a clear direction of where and which cloud services can be used.

Respondent D:

In addition to what you have, I think one vital area you need to look into is regulation and compliance. An instance would be that most financial institutions will not put so critical infrastructure on a cloud platform that is located outside their country. This considers mostly the confidentiality and privacy of individual data within the financial organisation; as such, the framework should also consider this.

Question 3:

- a) Is the CCMF leading to a better grasp of the challenges involved in decision-making?

Respondent A:

Yes, it does. It covers a wide range of areas.

Respondent B:

I believe that it leads. Although the financial impact is often a major factor, it is vital to remember that other factors also have a role. There are times when the operational risk of utilising a particular infrastructure is high enough to make it necessary to make a decision. Financial considerations will undoubtedly impact the infrastructure you

decide to use. Even if you opt for the most affordable infrastructure, if you later decide that you need to migrate to the cloud, we may encounter a scenario where issues around the operations might have more of an impact than finance.

Respondent C:

Certainly, without a doubt, as I have already mentioned, it does take into consideration the technologies being utilized presently, which is contained in the portfolio of applications. Another aspect is considering if the applications currently running are suitable for cloud migration within the company. Which is not a cost-oriented starting point, though. Furthermore, looking at the present infrastructure which was purchased for a certain reason, do they satisfy the needs? Also, noting that the present infrastructure is an investment, is their return on this investment? This are some of the fundamentals of meeting the set criteria. Within your discussion of cloud migration, it seems not to be about its effectiveness or meeting some needs, but about increased value. Which changes the topic of discourse to productivity. In order for something to be effective, it must be able to accomplish its intended purpose.

Respondent D:

The CCMF definitely give a clear definition of the problems faced by organisations with making the right decisions concerning cloud migration.

Question 4:

- a) Is the CCMF explicit and detailed on the steps to take?
- b) Is it simple to understand the CCMF procedure?
- c) Is implementing CCMF easy without guidance?

Respondent A:

I feel it talks more about the strategies used within the business, and from a business point of view, yes, it might be big enough. Considering it from the technological point of view, interoperability is a factor I see as lacking. Additionally, we need to consider architectural concepts. One fundamental question that comes to mind as a company is whether to adopt cutting-edge innovation or rather stick to tried and well-known methods. The advantage that your company has is provided through the concepts relating to its type. Most often, the decision to migrate is spearheaded by the architectural team. Definitely, there are parts of your framework that evaluates for

dependability and eligibility. The assessment of value phase is more of a corporate evaluation. In phase III, which focuses on the readiness of the organisation to migrate to the cloud, architectural concepts can be applied. Lastly, regarding the implementation of the CCMF without guidance, it is a yes from me.

Respondent B:

I would say it can be implemented without guidance but needs possibly additional explanation before going into various phases. Next would be my considerations over the procedure used. I feel they should have an initiation and termination point, which clearly states the decision and impact of the decision at every phase. It is important to have nothing left open, and the loop needs to be closed. Using a process or flow chart to navigate through can be helpful. However, it must be done with considerations for choices that are logical and have precise outcomes.

Respondent C:

The process is straightforward to implement; it links technological expenditures to business objectives. But it seems not too clear to me how the implementation commences after assessment. The CCMF is quite sequential, let me put it that way. You don't need any help from anyone. It's simple and easy to understand.

Respondent D:

It is detailed in steps, but doesn't look sequential to me. Looking at how simple the CCMF procedure is to understand. I would say it relies on your available resources, such as the number of individuals and how you intend to present the framework. For instance, an individual in operations would consider whether to hold or execute the BSC concurrently.

Question 5:

- a) Is anything in the CCMF unnecessary?
- b) What CCMF aspect is not necessary for the cloud migration decision-making process?

Respondent A:

I am unsure how the growth and learning viewpoint should be implemented or where it should be placed. It could be aligned into phase III, which addresses organisational readiness.

Respondent B:

I do not seem to see anything unnecessary from my perspective. Regarding the decision-making process, all the phases were actually defined and clear.

Respondent C:

From my perspective, I do not see a need for two separate phases for I and II. The eligibility and value evaluation phases should collapse to one phase. You need to consider the reliability and availability factors on a per-system basis. This might warrant looking deep into what are the necessary features from the BSC.

Respondent D:

My response is straightforward. Nothing is unnecessary in both areas of the question.

Question 6:

- a) What modifications to the CCMF would you propose?
- b) Does CCMF require any further features to make it more comprehensive?

Respondent A:

A question on market dynamics, on whether to take the lead or follow. I think looking at the angle of adopting a particular cloud service before others because it is affordable and taking the lead in its utilisation can also be considered.

Respondent B:

You might want to consider implementing the cloud migration process all at once or in various stages. It is also a consideration to look into. This is because you also need to consider how these changes will impact the organisations/businesses that are migrating. It is necessary to look at the core features of strategy implementation, which include awareness, training and communication across board.

Respondent C:

I have been able to cover most of this in my previous response.

Respondent D:

The feature which I would recommend is for you to consider the compliance and regulatory aspect. Having to determine the appropriate regulations associated with the infrastructure to be employed.